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Introduction

Information Technology (IT) and Data Science field relies on data and technology. It provides the infrastructure for data collection and storage and often needs to access and manage data effectively. The eight components to support IT and Data Science are 1). Data Structures and Algorithms, 2). Statistical Analysis for Data Science 3). Data Analytics and Visualization, 4). Big Data Technologies and Analytics, 5). Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence, 6). Programming languages and software development, 7). Cloud Computing and Distributed Systems, 8). Ethical and Legal Issues Related to Data Science. As stated by Kumar (2023), “And because of this huge amount of data the value of the field of Data Science has a number of advantages. Some of the advantages are mentioned below: Multiple Job Options: Being in demand, it has given rise to a large number of career opportunities in its various fields. Some of them are Data Scientist, Data Analyst, Research Analyst, Business Analyst, Analytics Manager, Big Data Engineer, etc. Business benefits: Data Science helps organizations knowing how and when their products sell best and that’s why the products are delivered always to the right place and right time. Faster and better decisions are taken by the organization to improve efficiency and earn higher profits. Highly Paid jobs & career opportunities: As Data Scientist continues being the sexiest job and the salaries for this position are also grand. Hiring benefits: It has made it comparatively easier to sort data and look for best of candidates for an organization. Big Data and data mining have made processing and selection of CVs, aptitude tests and games easier for the recruitment teams.” The objective of this report is to write ‘A. Capstone Project Route’ to complete the Master of Science in IT and Data Science. This Capstone Project involves applying IT and Data Science skills to a real-world problem to develop a web-based application for the solution that solves the problem. The project is Developing a Web-Based Application to implement Data Science namely, DATANA (DATA ANALYSIS) which aims to centralize, analyze, and visualize data of selected companies.

Main Body

1. Problem Statement and Project Scope

1.1. Problem Statement

After a discussion with a client who is the owner of several business companies, there are two companies that he is very concerned about including PTC Workshop and RACHNA Computer located in Kampot province, Cambodia. PTC Workshop is a company that provides vehicle repair services and sells spare parts. RACHNA Computer company sells electronic devices such as laptops, desktops, printers, accessories, and so on. These two companies have their web-based management application to manage the data. These two platforms are developed by using front-end languages HTML, CSS, JavaScript, and Bootstrap and the back-end language is PHP with MySQL database.

Figure 1. Website of PTC Workshop

The web-based application of PTC Workshop (figure 1) has many functionalities such as creating invoices, listing invoices, listing histories of repair services, and storing vehicle brands or spare parts. Moreover, the system also manages staff such as storing staff information, salary, attendance, or managing expenses. It also produces some reports with statistical data including net incomes, salary expenses, assets, utility expenses, and service income. Even though it provides many functionalities to use it still has limitations especially statical data and the data prediction for the future. The owner of the company wants to see more about many functionalities such as vehicle brand numbers, invoice numbers or sale statistics data, a summary of the total price of invoices for all days or separated by month and year, and product quantity in inventory. Moreover, for the PTC Workshop, he also needs to predict the income of the next months from invoices in the future.

RACHNA Computer also has its web-based application (figure 2) to create a point of sales (POS), manage sales, list and manage electronic products, and categories. Moreover, the system also manages staff and suppliers. It does not produce statistical reports related to sales, products, categories, staff, or suppliers. It is very limited to the owner of the company to see more about many functionalities related to statistics. The owner needs to have the statistical data including the number of products, categories, and suppliers, the number or summary of sales for the whole records or separated by month and year. Additionally, product quantities in stock are separated by products, purchasing quantity by month and year. Moreover, for the RACHNA Computer, he also needs to predict the income of the next months from sales in the future.

Figure 2. Website of RACHNA Computer

The Problem statement of the company’s owner is that he wants to understand the statistical data of his two companies and to estimate the sale and invoice income of the companies in the future. It means the systems lack advanced data analytics and forecasting capabilities. So, companies need enhanced statistical reporting and predictive insights to improve decision-making related to staff attendance, inventory, sales, income forecasting, and so on. This project will focus on enhancing both companies' web-based systems by incorporating data science techniques for statistical analysis, predictive modeling, and reporting. The main factors include data collection, data preprocessing, model development, and integration of insights into the existing management systems. The project addresses a typical need in IT-driven business management to leverage data

science for actionable insights. It involves the application of machine learning and statistical techniques to enhance business intelligence, optimize operations, and enable better forecasting.

1.2. Project Scope

The objective of the solution is to develop a web-based application that can perform statical data and perform regression model that predicts future income based on existing databases. Then the project scope is working on databases of PTC Workshop and RACHNA Computer by applying IT and Data Science to solve the problem as following including:

- Install and run Apache Hadoop to store and process large datasets across a distributed network of computers of PTC Workshop and RACHNA Computer.
- Apply Apache Sqoop to transfer bulk data between Apache Hadoop and relational databases such as MySQL databases of PTC Workshop and RACHNA Computer.
- Develop Django framework to build a web-based application to perform and view statical data results and perform a regression model that predicts the future income based on existing datasets in Apache Hadoop.
- Register an Amazon Web Services (AWS) account and create an Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2) instance to run Apache Hadoop.
- Run the Ubuntu Linux Operating System in EC2 to handle Apache Hadoop's services.
- Attach Amazon Elastic Block (EBS) to store Django project separately in EC2.
- Configure Application Load Balancer (ABL) in AWS to manage load and improve application reliability
- Implement Auto Scaling Group (ASG) to adjust the number of EC2 instances based on demand.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Comprehensive Review

Big Data Technologies: “Big data technology is defined as software-utility. This technology is primarily designed to analyze, process and extract information from a large data set and a huge set of extremely complex structures. This is very difficult for traditional data processing software

to deal with. Among the larger concepts of rage in technology, big data technologies are widely associated with many other technologies such as deep learning, machine learning, artificial intelligence (AI), and Internet of Things (IoT) that are massively augmented. In combination with these technologies, big data technologies are focused on analyzing and handling large amounts of real-time data and batch-related data” (*Big Data Technologies - Javatpoint*, n.d.). After applying it to the business, companies will gain benefits such as expanded business intelligence, enhanced user targeting, improved customer service, increased efficiency and reduced costs, influenced customer behavior, lower operational risk, and so on.

Big Data Processing: “Big data processing covers collecting, storing, and managing massive amounts of data (mostly in a semi- or unstructured form) that arrives from multiple sources. Big data processing stages include data ingestion into a data lake or a stream processing engine, data cleansing and transformation, and data loading into an analytics storage optimized for querying and reporting. Processed big data is used to derive insights (including real-time) and trigger immediate automated actions” (*Big Data Processing: A Comprehensive Guide for 2024*, n.d.). One of the best Big Data Processing is Apache Hadoop, it has gained prominence as a scalable framework for processing and storing large volumes of data across distributed systems, making it an essential component in handling big data analytics for businesses. The integration of Hadoop allows companies to conduct deeper analyses, extract valuable insights, and store massive amounts of data for historical comparison. For companies with relational databases, such as MySQL, Apache Sqoop is commonly used to transfer data into Hadoop for advanced processing. Hadoop is being used for business analytics, predictive modeling, and large-scale data management, focusing on industries that align with PTC Workshop and RACHNA Computer companies.

Data Ingestion: Cognizant.com wrote that “Data ingestion is the process of importing large, assorted data files from multiple sources into a single, cloud-based storage medium - a data warehouse, data mart or database where it can be accessed and analyzed. As data may be in multiple different forms and come from hundreds of sources, it is sanitized and transformed into a uniform format using an extract/transform/load (ETL) process” (*Data Ingestion*, n.d.). The role of Apache Sqoop is the processing of Data Ingestion or Data Integration between relational

databases (RDBMS) and Apache Hadoop ecosystems. Apache Sqoop is utilized to manage bulk data transfer and maintain consistency between data stores.

Web Development for Data Visualization: Sykes (2018) mentioned that, “Data visualization is the presentation of data through pictures, graphs, and other visual mediums. It allows decision makers to see analytics so they can grasp complex concepts and connect the dots to find new patterns. Technology allows us to take data visualization even further by adding interactivity, so users can drill down into charts and graphs for more detail to change their view of the data. Because of the way humans processes information, data visualization makes it easier to understand complex data than viewing the same information in spreadsheets or reports.” And the w3school.com also stated, “Django is a Python framework that makes it easier to create web sites using Python. Django takes care of the difficult stuff so that you can concentrate on building your web applications. Django emphasizes reusability of components, also referred to as DRY (Don't Repeat Yourself), and comes with ready-to-use features like login system, database connection and CRUD operations (Create Read Update Delete)” (*W3Schools.com*, n.d.). Django is used as a robust web framework for building data-intensive applications and many Django-based tools and libraries support statistical data display, including insights into how businesses use visualizations to support decision-making.

Data Analytics and Machine Learning in SMEs: They have emerged opportunities and allows SMEs to remain competitive by providing a clearer understanding of customer behavior, financial health, and operational efficiency. These technologies help companies make sense of historical data to forecast future trends, optimize operations, and improve customer satisfaction. Machine learning techniques, especially regression models, are commonly applied for financial forecasting, which has proven to improve budget planning and resource allocation in SMEs (Dikov, 2024).

Predictive Modeling: From qlik.com, Predictive modeling uses past data to guess future outcomes. It builds a math model with input details to predict results. Machine learning improves these models to help make better decisions. It's used in many areas like finding fraud, grouping customers, diagnosing diseases, and predicting stock prices (*What Is Predictive Modeling? Types & Techniques*, n.d.). The regression and machine learning models are used for income and

revenue prediction and these techniques help businesses make proactive decisions based on data to evaluate predictive models' accuracy and reliability in business applications, and why certain models may be more effective in predicting future trends.

Cloud Computing and Scalability: BasuMallick (2024) defined “Cloud computing refers to the use of hosted services, such as data storage, servers, databases, networking, and software over the internet. The data is stored on physical servers, which are maintained by a cloud service provider.” Amazon Web Services (AWS), Google Cloud Platform (GCP) and Ms. Azure are the most popular Cloud Service Providers (CSP). Scalability are Load Balancing and Auto-scaling that improve reliability, especially in systems that experience variable traffic, as is expected with the growing needs of businesses.

2.2. Critical Evaluation of Existing Research and Identification of Gaps

Limited Accessibility of Advanced Analytics for SMEs: While the benefits of data analytics for forecasting and decision-making are well-documented, most solutions are tailored to larger enterprises with more resources. There is limited research on practical, cost-effective solutions for SMEs, particularly those operating in less developed regions. However, D (2023) reports that most SMEs lack advanced analytics due to Limited Resources, Data Quality and Accuracy, Data Security and Privacy, Data Integration, and a lack of Data Storage and Scalability. Small businesses often struggle to deploy ML algorithms because there are lacks of Inaccessible Data and Data Security, Infrastructure Requirements for Testing & Experimentation, Rigid Business Models, Lack of Talent, Time-Consuming Implementation, and Affordability (Sname, 2020).

Challenges in Deploying Big Data Infrastructure in SMEs: The literature suggests that while Hadoop and Sqoop offer robust data handling and analysis capabilities, their deployment is primarily discussed within the context of large enterprises or research institutions. These technologies are very challenges in developing country like Cambodia because of the limitation of guidance, budgets or technical expertise to apply.

Cloud Computing for Scalable and Cost-Effective Infrastructure: Cloud computing has transformed the way businesses deploy and manage applications by providing on-demand resources, scalability, and cost savings. Several services of AWS are Elastic Compute Cloud

(EC2), Elastic Block Store (EBS), Application Load Balancing (ALB) and Auto Scaling Group (ASG) offer SMEs the flexibility to scale resources based on demand, reducing costs while ensuring application availability.

Scalable Cloud Solutions for SMEs in Developing Markets: While cloud services like AWS provide scalable, cost-effective solutions, research has primarily focused on developed markets. There is a need for guidance on implementing these services within budget constraints, as well as adapting them for SMEs in emerging markets.

Integration of Predictive Models in Existing Systems: Few studies explore the practical integration of predictive analytics into legacy or existing web-based management systems commonly used by SMEs. By enhancing the existing PHP-based systems of PTC Workshop and RACHNA Computer with a Django-based analytics platform, this project bridges the gap between data science and legacy systems, providing a more actionable, data-driven approach to business management. Some researchers note that a gap in research around the implementation of Sqoop in smaller enterprises with limited technical resources, particularly in non-traditional markets. Another Sqoop's limitations and challenges, such as data consistency issues or transfer speed concerns.

2.3. Synthesizing of Literature Review

Big data technologies: It has significantly transformed the landscape of data analytics, providing businesses with enhanced capabilities for processing large volumes of data and making more informed decisions. These technologies, when integrated with tools like ML, AI, and the IoT, offer powerful advantages such as real-time data handling, predictive analytics, and operational efficiency. However, while the potential benefits of big data are well-established, the adoption and implementation of these technologies in SMEs, particularly in developing economic countries (Cambodia), remains limited due to constraints such as budget limitations, technical expertise gaps, and data quality issues.

Big data processing: The significance of frameworks like Apache Hadoop and Apache Sqoop for handling vast datasets. These tools allow businesses to perform complex analyses and store large volumes of data across distributed systems, contributing to business intelligence and

predictive modeling. However, most studies on these technologies focus on large enterprises, with few offering practical guidance on how SMEs especially those in low-resource environments like Cambodia can implement them effectively.

Data Ingestion and Cloud Computing (Scalable and cost-effective solutions): Cloud platforms like AWS provide SMEs with flexible infrastructure, reducing operational costs while ensuring scalability and reliability. However, research focused on the use of cloud computing in developed country has some significant gaps, such as understanding how these solutions are adapted to meet the unique challenges of SMEs in developing regions.

Data Analytics and Machine Learning Techniques: particularly in predictive modeling, offer SMEs valuable insights into customer behavior, financial health, and operational efficiency. These technologies enable SMEs to make proactive decisions based on historical data, improving areas like financial forecasting and resource allocation. Despite the promise of these technologies, the practical integration of predictive models into existing systems used by SMEs is often overlooked. There is a critical gap in research on how to effectively integrate predictive analytics into legacy systems, such as those based on PHP or other traditional platforms.

Data Visualization: While the advantages of data visualization tools are widely acknowledged, few studies address how SMEs can effectively utilize these tools to enhance decision-making, particularly within data-intensive applications developed using frameworks like Django. Furthermore, the integration of predictive models into such applications, enabling actionable insights from data visualizations, remains an under-explored area, especially in the context of SMEs.

Project Synthesizing: This project leverages AWS EC2, EBS, ALB, and ASG to provide a robust, scalable infrastructure tailored to the requirements of PTC Workshop and RACHNA Computer. By using these services, the project not only ensures high availability and reliability but also makes advanced technology accessible to businesses in a cost-efficient manner. The integration of cloud-based scalability addresses the challenges of limited technical resources, enabling companies to efficiently manage fluctuating workloads without requiring extensive technical expertise. This project addresses this by deploying a simplified Hadoop ecosystem on AWS with Sqoop, optimized to handle the specific data requirements of PTC Workshop and

RACHNA Computer while reducing infrastructure complexity. This project addresses this gap by implementing predictive analytics in the form of a regression model within a Django-based web application that integrates seamlessly with the existing data management systems of PTC Workshop and RACHNA Computer. By utilizing an accessible web interface and automating data-driven insights, this approach aims to make advanced predictive analytics more approachable for SMEs.

3. Data Collection and Preprocessing

3.1. Data Collection

The overall technologies, tools, and operating systems used in this project, including Apache Hadoop, Apache Sqoop, and HDFS Architecture work in Ubuntu Linux OS and Django web-based application for Data Visualization and Regression Model Analysis for prediction. The project's scenario first is importing datasets from the database of the companies by using Apache Sqoop in Apache Hadoop, second is activating a virtual environment, third is cleaning, preparing, and preprocessing data by using Python, fourth is analyzing data by using Django, and fifth is visualizing data by import data from Hadoop File System to Django to visualize and summarize statistical data.

Before working on data ingestion and collection, Ubuntu Linux OS needs to be tested to make sure Apache Hadoop and its services are running by using these commands “**cd /usr/local/hadoop/sbin**” and “**./start-all.sh**” in Terminal.


```
root@ip-172-31-25-26: /usr/local/hadoop/sbin
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/# cd /usr/local/hadoop/sbin
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/usr/local/hadoop/sbin# ./start-all.sh
This script is deprecated. Instead use start-dfs.sh and start-yarn.sh
24/11/16 14:19:29 WARN util.NativeCodeLoader: Unable to load native-hadoop library for your platform... using builtin-java classes where applicable
Starting namenodes on [localhost]
localhost: starting namenode, logging to /usr/local/hadoop/logs/hadoop-root-name
node-ip-172-31-25-26.out
localhost: starting datanode, logging to /usr/local/hadoop/logs/hadoop-root-data
node-ip-172-31-25-26.out
Starting secondary namenodes [0.0.0.0]
0.0.0.0: starting secondarynamenode, logging to /usr/local/hadoop/logs/hadoop-ro
ot-secondarynamenode-ip-172-31-25-26.out
24/11/16 14:19:49 WARN util.NativeCodeLoader: Unable to load native-hadoop libra
ry for your platform... using builtin-java classes where applicable
starting yarn daemons
```

Figure 3. Starting Apache Hadoop Application

Type 'jps' command to verify running services of Apache Hadoop.

```
root@ip-172-31-25-26: /usr/local/hadoop/sbin
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/usr/local/hadoop/sbin# jps
3200 DataNode
3393 SecondaryNameNode
3969 Jps
3530 ResourceManager
3019 NameNode
3646 NodeManager
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/usr/local/hadoop/sbin#
```

Figure 4. Using 'jps' command to displays Hadoop running services

Apache Sqoop is another effective data ingestion and pre-processing technique used to ingest datasets from another database server. It is very handful to connect the dataset from the SQL Queries to the Hadoop distributed file system (GeeksforGeeks, 2021).

Figure 5. MySQL Database of PTC Workshop company

To allow Sqoop can connect and import data from a database server, it needs some information including server name, database name, database username, database user password, and database

port number. So, to connect to the company’s database Sqoop needs the database information of PTC Workshop as Server: ‘sql12.freemysqlhosting.net’, Name: ‘sql12744702’, Username: ‘sql12744702’, Password: ‘Jr12QFBUTg’ and Port number: ‘3306’.

For database information of RACHNA Computer provided below for Sqoop connection are Server: ‘sql12.freemysqlhosting.net’, Name: ‘sql12743239’, Username: ‘sql12743239’, Password: ‘vRxc4eCABS’ and Port number: ‘3306’.

Figure 6. MySQL Database of RACHNA Computer company

The command below is used to check the information in the Hadoop file system the result is nothing except the ‘tmp’ folder.

hadoop fs -ls /

```
root@ip-172-31-25-26: /usr/local/hadoop/sbin
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/usr/local/hadoop/sbin# hadoop fs -ls /
24/11/16 15:13:31 WARN util.NativeCodeLoader: Unable to load native-hadoop library for your platform... using builtin-java classes where applicable
Found 5 items
drwxr-xr-x - root supergroup      0 2024-11-11 10:49 /home
drwxr-xr-x - root supergroup      0 2024-11-14 15:17 /pos
drwxr-xr-x - root supergroup      0 2024-11-14 15:19 /ptc
drwxr-xr-x - root supergroup      0 2024-11-11 11:22 /tmp
drwxr-xr-x - root supergroup      0 2024-08-03 15:47 /user
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/usr/local/hadoop/sbin#
```

Figure 7. The information in Hadoop file system

Because there are many service files to start and many tables for Sqoop to import, so there is a file name 'start.sh' is created to store bash shell scripts to execute in 3 tasks sequentially, including first is starting Apache Hadoop services, second is running Sqoop's service to import selected tables from RACHNA database and PTC Workshop database, and third is starting Django virtual environment service.

/penv/start.sh

```
#!/bin/bash
```

```
#1. Start Hadoop
```

```
/usr/local/hadoop/sbin/start-all.sh
```

```
#2. Import tables from remote database by using Sqoop
```

```
#RACHNA Computer Database
```

```
pos_tables=("table_category" "table_customer" "table_product" "table_sale" "table_stock"
"table_supplier")
```

```
pos_mysql_host="jdbc:mysql://sql12.freemysqlhosting.net/sql12743239"
```

```
pos_mysql_user="sql12743239"
```

```
pos_mysql_password="vRxg4eCABS"
```

```

for pos_table in "${pos_tables[@]}"; do

    hadoop fs -rm -r -f "/pos/$pos_table"

    sqoop import --connect "$pos_mysql_host" --username "$pos_mysql_user" --password
"$pos_mysql_password" \

    --table "$pos_table" --target-dir "/pos/$pos_table" --fields-terminated-by ',' --lines-terminated-
by '\n'

    hadoop fs -getmerge "/pos/$pos_table" "/penv/datana/datana/datasets/pos/$pos_table.csv"

done

#PTC Workshop Database

ptc_tables=("table_attendance" "table_car" "table_invoice" "table_invoice_detail"
"table_product" "table_salary" "table_staff" "table_staff_type" "table_stock" "table_utility")

ptc_mysql_host="jdbc:mysql://sql12.freemysqlhosting.net/sql12744702"

ptc_mysql_user="sql12744702"

ptc_mysql_password="Jr12QFBUTg"

for ptc_table in "${ptc_tables[@]}"; do

    hadoop fs -rm -r -f "/ptc/$ptc_table"

    sqoop import --connect "$ptc_mysql_host" --username "$ptc_mysql_user" --password
"$ptc_mysql_password" \

    --table "$ptc_table" --target-dir "/ptc/$ptc_table" --fields-terminated-by ',' --lines-terminated-
by '\n'

    hadoop fs -getmerge "/ptc/$ptc_table" "/penv/datana/datana/datasets/ptc/$ptc_table.csv"

done

```

#3. Activate Virtual Environment

```
source /pen/denv/bin/activate
```

The Sqoop command lines in 'start.sh' are used to connect and import datasets from the company's databases by using Sqoop syntax followed by the provided database information.

```
sqoop import --connect jdbc:mysql://sql12.freemysqlhosting.net/sql12723594 --username <username> --password <password> --table <table name> --target-dir <dir in HDFS>
```

As stated by How Sqoop Internally Works (2018), “Sqoop is running a map-only job which each mapper running a query with a specific range to prevent any kind of overlap. The mapper then just drops the data in the target-dir HDFS directory with a file named part-m-00000 (well, the 2nd on ends with 00001 and the 3rd one ends with 00002). The composite export is represented by the target-dir HDFS directory (basically follows the MapReduce naming scheme of files).” To validate the imported data, the following command lines are used to list contain, for example in the ‘/pos/pos_sale’ directory, and display all data in the ‘/pos/table_sale/part-m-0000*’ file.

```
hadoop fs -cat /pos/table_sale/part-m-0000*
```



```
root@ip-172-31-25-26: /
0.0,150.0,600000.0,4500.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,1
572,2024-10-07 11:44:58.0,1,360.0,1440000.0,10800.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,360.0,1440000.0,
10800.0,360.0,1440000.0,10800.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,1
573,2024-10-07 11:44:58.0,1,360.0,1440000.0,10800.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,360.0,1440000.0,
10800.0,360.0,1440000.0,10800.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,1
574,2024-10-07 11:44:28.0,1,150.0,600000.0,4500.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,150.0,600000.0,450
0.0,150.0,600000.0,4500.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,1
575,2024-10-07 11:44:12.0,1,530.0,2120000.0,15900.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,530.0,2120000.0,
15900.0,530.0,2120000.0,15900.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,1
576,2024-10-07 11:44:12.0,1,530.0,2120000.0,15900.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,530.0,2120000.0,
15900.0,530.0,2120000.0,15900.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,1
577,2024-10-07 11:44:28.0,1,150.0,600000.0,4500.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,150.0,600000.0,450
0.0,150.0,600000.0,4500.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,1
578,2024-10-07 11:44:58.0,1,360.0,1440000.0,10800.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,360.0,1440000.0,
10800.0,360.0,1440000.0,10800.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,1
579,2024-10-07 11:44:58.0,1,360.0,1440000.0,10800.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,360.0,1440000.0,
10800.0,360.0,1440000.0,10800.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,1
580,2024-10-07 11:44:28.0,1,150.0,600000.0,4500.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,150.0,600000.0,450
0.0,150.0,600000.0,4500.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,1
581,2024-10-07 11:44:12.0,1,530.0,2120000.0,15900.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,530.0,2120000.0,
15900.0,530.0,2120000.0,15900.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,1
582,2024-10-07 11:44:12.0,1,530.0,2120000.0,15900.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,530.0,2120000.0,
15900.0,530.0,2120000.0,15900.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,1
root@ip-172-31-25-26: /#
```

Figure 8. Displaying the data content

The result displays all the data of the imported dataset in part-m-00000, part-m-00001, part-m-00002, and part-m-00003 until the last part.

After importing, the 'hadoop fs -getmerge' command is used to convert and merge '**part-m-0000***' to the *.csv file. Shell scripts in 'start.sh' will process this technique and store all CSV files in the '/penv/datana/datana/datasets' directory. This directory is in the virtual environment of the Django project for use to clean and analyze in the next tasks.


```
root@ip-172-31-25-26: /
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/# tree /penv/datana/datana/datasets/
/penv/datana/datana/datasets/
├── pos
│   ├── table_category.csv
│   ├── table_customer.csv
│   ├── table_product.csv
│   ├── table_sale.csv
│   ├── table_stock.csv
│   └── table_supplier.csv
└── ptc
    ├── table_attendance.csv
    ├── table_car.csv
    ├── table_invoice.csv
    ├── table_invoice_detail.csv
    ├── table_product.csv
    ├── table_salary.csv
    ├── table_staff.csv
    ├── table_staff_type.csv
    ├── table_stock.csv
    └── table_utility.csv

3 directories, 16 files
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/#
```

Figure 9. List Django project's contents

3.2. Data Preprocessing

After data is collected, it must be cleaned, transformed, and prepared for analysis. This step involves multiple preprocessing tasks to ensure the data is consistent, accurate, and usable for statistical modeling and prediction. These preprocessing steps ensure data is ready for statistical analysis and predictive modeling. Clean, normalized, and well-structured data will lead to more accurate statistical summaries and reliable predictions, helping the company's owner gain valuable insights into the operations and future growth potential of his businesses.

3.2.1. Data Cleaning

Handling Missing Values: “The concept of missing data is implied in the name: it’s data that is not captured for a variable for the observation in question. Missing data can skew all kinds of tasks for data scientists, from economic analyses to clinical trials. After all, any analysis is only as good as the data used. A data scientist doesn’t want to produce biased estimates that lead to invalid results. Fortunately, there are proven techniques to deal with missing data” (*How to Deal With Missing Data | Master’s in Data Science, 2024*). Any missing or incomplete entries in the datasets are identified. Missing values are either filled with median/mean values where appropriate or removed if the records are not critical for analysis. In PTC Workshop datasets, the analysis is not for all tables, some tables are used also to analyze following the matched criteria. In ‘table_invoice’ table must be checked missing values on ‘invoice_date’ and ‘grand_total’ columns because they need to use the next task to predict ‘sales in the future based on sales of the current month and year’. For RACHNA Computer datasets are checked for missing value on ‘sale_date’ and ‘grand_total_usd’ on ‘table_sale’ table in ‘sales in the future based on sales of current month and year’. File names “/penv/remove_missing.py” is created with code below:

```
#!/usr/bin/env python3

import pandas as pd

file_path1 = '/penv/datana/datana/datasets/ptc/table_invoice.csv'

file_path3 = '/penv/datana/datana/datasets/pos/table_sale.csv'

df1 = pd.read_csv(file_path1)

df_cleaned1 = df1.dropna(subset=[df1.columns[1], df1.columns[8]], how='any')

df_cleaned1.to_csv(file_path1, index=False)

df_cleaned2.to_csv(file_path2, index=False)

df3 = pd.read_csv(file_path3)

df_cleaned3 = df3.dropna(subset=[df3.columns[1], df3.columns[9]], how='any')

df_cleaned3.to_csv(file_path3, index=False)
```

3.2.2. Data Transformation

Outlier Detection and Removal: The GeeksforGeeks (2024) stated, “An Outlier is a data item/object that deviates significantly from the rest of the (so-called normal) objects. Identifying outliers is important in statistics and data analysis because they can have a significant impact on the results of statistical analyses. The analysis for outlier detection is referred to as outlier mining. Outliers can skew the mean (average) and affect measures of central tendency, as well as influence the results of tests of statistical significance.” Outliers in the dataset must be detected and reviewed. Outliers may be corrected based on business knowledge or removed if they represent data entry errors. For this case, one of the many ways to detect outliers is using Interquartile Range (IQR). In PTC Workshop datasets, the analysis is not for all tables, some tables are used also to analyze following the matched criteria. In ‘table_invoice’ table must be checked and outliers on ‘invoice_date’ with ‘grand_total’ columns because they need to use next task to predict ‘sales in the future based on sales of current month and year’. For RACHNA Computer datasets are checked and remove outliers on ‘sale_date’ with ‘grand_total_usd’ on ‘table_sale’ table in ‘sales in the future based on sales of current month and year’.

```
/penv/remove_outliers.py
```

```
#!/usr/bin/env python3
```

```
import pandas as pd
```

```
file_path1 = '/penv/datana/datana/datasets/ptc/table_invoice.csv'
```

```
file_path_output1 = '/penv/datana/datana/datasets/ptc/table_invoice_iqr.csv'
```

```
df1 = pd.read_csv(file_path1)
```

```
selected_columns1 = df1.iloc[:, [1, 8]]
```

```
Q1_1 = selected_columns1.iloc[:, 1].quantile(0.25)
```

```
Q3_1 = selected_columns1.iloc[:, 1].quantile(0.75)
```

```
IQR_1 = Q3_1 - Q1_1
```

```

lower_bound1 = Q1_1 - 1.5 * IQR_1

upper_bound1 = Q3_1 + 1.5 * IQR_1

df_no_outliers1 = df1[(df1.iloc[:, 8] >= lower_bound1) & (df1.iloc[:, 8] <= upper_bound1)]

df_no_outliers1.to_csv(file_path_output1, index=False)

file_path3 = '/penv/datana/datana/datasets/pos/table_sale.csv'

file_path_output3 = '/penv/datana/datana/datasets/pos/table_sale_iqr.csv'

df3 = pd.read_csv(file_path3)

selected_columns3 = df3.iloc[:, [1, 9]]

Q1_3 = selected_columns3.iloc[:, 1].quantile(0.25)

Q3_3 = selected_columns3.iloc[:, 1].quantile(0.75)

IQR_3 = Q3_3 - Q1_3

lower_bound3 = Q1_3 - 1.5 * IQR_3

upper_bound3 = Q3_3 + 1.5 * IQR_3

df_no_outliers3 = df3[(df3.iloc[:, 9] >= lower_bound3) & (df3.iloc[:, 9] <= upper_bound3)]

df_no_outliers3.to_csv(file_path_output3, index=False)

```

4. Data Analysis and Modelling

4.1. Data Analysis Techniques and Statistical Methods

The data analysis and statistical methods phase involves processing and examining the datasets collected from both the PTC Workshop and RACHNA Computer. By leveraging data science techniques, statistical analysis, and visualizations, insights are generated to support decision-making for the business's owner. Data analysis uses statistical methods such as sum, mean,

median, mode, range, variance, standard deviation, and skewness can be applied with Django to perform the calculation. For the PTC Workshop, the Statistical Methods were calculated related to invoice income based on 'table_invoice_iqr.csv' file.

File name: “/penv/datana/datana/views.py”

```
def workshop_statistic_view(request):

    csv_file_path = '/penv/datana/datana/datasets/ptc/table_invoice_iqr.csv'

    df = pd.read_csv(csv_file_path)

    df.rename(columns={'Col_1': 'invoice_date', 'Col_8': 'grand_total'}, inplace=True)

    if 'invoice_date' not in df.columns or 'grand_total' not in df.columns:

        return render(request, 'workshop_statistic.html', {

            'error': "Required columns ('invoice_date', 'grand_total') are missing from the CSV."

        })

    grand_totals = df['grand_total']

    statistics = {

        'total': np.sum(grand_totals),

        'mean': np.mean(grand_totals),

        'median': np.median(grand_totals),

        'mode': stats.mode(grand_totals, keepdims=True)[0][0],

        'range': np.ptp(grand_totals),

        'variance': np.var(grand_totals),

        'std_dev': np.std(grand_totals),
```

```
'skewness': stats.skew(grand_totals)

}

return render(request, 'workshop_statistic.html', {'stats': statistics})
```

File name: “/penv/datana/datana/templates/workshop_statistic.html”

```
<div class="row">

    <div class="col-md-12">

        <h1>PTC Workshop / Sale Statistic</h1>

    </div>

    <div class="col-md-12">

        {% if stats %}

        <div class="table-responsive">

            <table class="table table-striped table-bordered">

                <thead class="thead-dark">

                    <tr>

                        <th>Statistic</th>

                        <th>Value (USD)</th>

                    </tr>

                </thead>

                <tbody>

                    <tr>
```

```
<td>Mean</td>

<td>{{ stats.mean }}</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>Median</td>

<td>{{ stats.median }}</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>Mode</td>

<td>{{ stats.mode }}</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>Range</td>

<td>{{ stats.range }}</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>Variance</td>

<td>{{ stats.variance }}</td>

</tr>

<tr>
```

```
<td>Standard Deviation</td>
```

```
<td>{{ stats.std_dev }}</td>
```

```
</tr>
```

```
<tr>
```

```
<td>Skewness</td>
```

```
<td>{{ stats.skewness }}</td>
```

```
</tr>
```

```
</tbody>
```

```
</table>
```

```
</div>
```

```
{% else %}
```

```
<p class="text-danger">No sales data available or an error occurred while processing  
the CSV.</p>
```

```
{% endif %}
```

```
</div>
```

DATANA RACHNA COMPUTER PTC WORKSHOP Logout																			
PTC Home	<h2>PTC Workshop / Sale Statistic</h2> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Statistic</th> <th>Value (USD)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td>678135.0149999999</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mean</td> <td>47.48844642857142</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Median</td> <td>36.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mode</td> <td>10.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Range</td> <td>178.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Variance</td> <td>1643.4846871434886</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Standard Deviation</td> <td>40.53991474020991</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Skewness</td> <td>1.111148498490739</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Statistic	Value (USD)	Total	678135.0149999999	Mean	47.48844642857142	Median	36.0	Mode	10.0	Range	178.0	Variance	1643.4846871434886	Standard Deviation	40.53991474020991	Skewness	1.111148498490739
Statistic		Value (USD)																	
Total		678135.0149999999																	
Mean		47.48844642857142																	
Median		36.0																	
Mode		10.0																	
Range		178.0																	
Variance		1643.4846871434886																	
Standard Deviation		40.53991474020991																	
Skewness		1.111148498490739																	
Attendance																			
Car																			
Sale Statistic																			
Sale Regression																			
Sale Prediction																			
Product																			
Salary																			
Staff																			
Stock																			
Utility																			

Figure 10. Statistical Methods Result of RACHNA Computer datasets on Django

Statistical summaries of RACHNA Computer were generated for sales data is also summarized by overall and by month and year to identify seasonal trends and fluctuations, allowing the company to understand peak sales periods and plan inventory accordingly.

File name: “/penv/datana/datana/views.py”

```
def computer_statistic_view(request):
```

```
    csv_file_path = '/penv/datana/datana/datasets/pos/table_sale_iqr.csv'
```

```
    df = pd.read_csv(csv_file_path)
```

```
    df.rename(columns={'Col_1': 'sale_date', 'Col_9': 'grand_total'}, inplace=True)
```

```
    if 'sale_date' not in df.columns or 'grand_total' not in df.columns:
```

```
        return render(request, 'computer_statistic.html', {
```

```
            'error': "Required columns ('sale_date', 'grand_total') are missing from the CSV."
```

```
        })
```

```

grand_totals = df['grand_total']

statistics = {

    'sum': np.sum(grand_totals),

    'mean': np.mean(grand_totals),

    'median': np.median(grand_totals),

    'mode': stats.mode(grand_totals, keepdims=True)[0][0],

    'range': np.ptp(grand_totals),

    'variance': np.var(grand_totals),

    'std_dev': np.std(grand_totals),

    'skewness': stats.skew(grand_totals)

}

return render(request, 'computer_statistic.html', {'stats': statistics})

```

File name: “/penv/datana/datana/templates/computer_statistic.html”

```

<div class="col-md-12">

    {% if stats %}

    <div class="table-responsive">

        <table class="table table-striped table-bordered">

            <thead class="thead-dark">

                <tr>

                    <th>Statistic</th>

```

```
        <th>Value (USD)</th>

    </tr>

</thead>

<tbody>

    <tr>

        <td>Total</td>

        <td>{{ stats.sum }}</td>

    </tr>

    <tr>

        <td>Mean</td>

        <td>{{ stats.mean }}</td>

    </tr>

    <tr>

        <td>Median</td>

        <td>{{ stats.median }}</td>

    </tr>

    <tr>

        <td>Mode</td>

        <td>{{ stats.mode }}</td>

    </tr>
```

```
<tr>

    <td>Range</td>

    <td>{{ stats.range }}</td>

</tr>

<tr>

    <td>Variance</td>

    <td>{{ stats.variance }}</td>

</tr>

<tr>

    <td>Standard Deviation</td>

    <td>{{ stats.std_dev }}</td>

</tr>

<tr>

    <td>Skewness</td>

    <td>{{ stats.skewness }}</td>

</tr>

</tbody>

</table>

</div>

{% else % }
```

<p class="text-danger">No sales data available or an error occurred while processing the CSV.</p>

{% endif % }

</div>

DATANA RACHNA COMPUTER PTC WORKSHOP Logout																			
RACHNA Home	<h2>RACHNA Computer / Sale Statistic</h2> <table border="1"><thead><tr><th>Statistic</th><th>Value (USD)</th></tr></thead><tbody><tr><td>Total</td><td>185697.0</td></tr><tr><td>Mean</td><td>441.0855106888361</td></tr><tr><td>Median</td><td>465.0</td></tr><tr><td>Mode</td><td>500.0</td></tr><tr><td>Range</td><td>1020.0</td></tr><tr><td>Variance</td><td>77229.73615585557</td></tr><tr><td>Standard Deviation</td><td>277.9023860204435</td></tr><tr><td>Skewness</td><td>0.533618003885907</td></tr></tbody></table>	Statistic	Value (USD)	Total	185697.0	Mean	441.0855106888361	Median	465.0	Mode	500.0	Range	1020.0	Variance	77229.73615585557	Standard Deviation	277.9023860204435	Skewness	0.533618003885907
Statistic		Value (USD)																	
Total		185697.0																	
Mean		441.0855106888361																	
Median		465.0																	
Mode		500.0																	
Range		1020.0																	
Variance		77229.73615585557																	
Standard Deviation		277.9023860204435																	
Skewness		0.533618003885907																	
Sale Statistic																			
Sale Regression																			
Sale Prediction																			
Categories																			
Customers																			
Products																			
Sales																			
Stocks																			
Suppliers																			

Figure 11. Statistical Methods Result of RACHNA Computer datasets on Django

4.2. Feature Engineering

To prepare the data for predictive modeling, important features were extracted from the raw datasets. For both companies, relevant features such as monthly total income, product quantities in stock, and sales were selected. These features were used to train the model for sale prediction.

Extract Date Components: As stated by Mondal (2024) stated, feature extraction is an important step in machine learning where raw data is changed into a form that's easier to use for building models. It means picking, mixing, and changing data parts to make machine learning work better. The 'invoice_date' column in 'table_invoice_iqr.csv' in PTC Workshop is transformed to extract useful features to 3 more columns (day, month, and year). And 'sale_date' column in 'table_sale_iqr.csv' of RACHNA Computer datasets is also extracted by adding into new 3 columns (day, month, and year) with a file names `"/penv/date_processing.py"`.

```

#!/usr/bin/env python3

import pandas as pd

file_path1 = '/penv/datana/datana/datasets/ptc/table_invoice_iqr.csv'

data1 = pd.read_csv(file_path1)

data1.columns = [f"Col_{i}" for i in range(data1.shape[1])]

data1['Col_1'] = pd.to_datetime(data1['Col_1'], errors='coerce')

data1['day'] = data1['Col_1'].dt.day

data1['month'] = data1['Col_1'].dt.month

data1['year'] = data1['Col_1'].dt.year

data1.rename(columns={"Col_1": "invoice_date"}, inplace=True)

data1.to_csv(file_path1, index=False)

file_path3 = '/penv/datana/datana/datasets/pos/table_sale_iqr.csv'

data3 = pd.read_csv(file_path3)

data3.columns = [f"Col_{i}" for i in range(data3.shape[1])]

data3['Col_1'] = pd.to_datetime(data3['Col_1'], errors='coerce')

data3['day'] = data3['Col_1'].dt.day

data3['month'] = data3['Col_1'].dt.month

data3['year'] = data3['Col_1'].dt.year

data3.rename(columns={"Col_1": "sale_date"}, inplace=True)

data3.to_csv(file_path3, index=False)

```

Frequency Encoding: As written by Ninja (2024), “Frequency encoding, often known as count encoding, is a common method employed in handling categorical data in machine learning. In frequency encoding, we replace each category with the count of how often it appears in the dataset. In other words, we substitute the category with its frequency.” For the PTC Workshop, additional features included monthly invoices and RACHNA Computer, a feature like monthly sales. The file names “/penv/frequency_encoding.py” is created with codes below:

```
#!/usr/bin/env python3

import pandas as pd

from datetime import datetime

file_path = '/penv/datana/datana/datasets/pos/table_sale_iqr.csv'

output_file = '/penv/datana/datana/datasets/pos/table_sale_fe.csv'

df = pd.read_csv(file_path)

df_filtered = df[['sale_date', 'Col_9']]

df_filtered.rename(columns={'Col_9': 'grand_total'}, inplace=True)

df_filtered['sale_date'] = pd.to_datetime(df_filtered['sale_date'])

df_filtered['month'] = df_filtered['sale_date'].dt.month

df_filtered['year'] = df_filtered['sale_date'].dt.year

df_grouped = df_filtered.groupby(['year', 'month'])['grand_total'].sum().reset_index()

df_grouped['sale_date'] = df_grouped['year'].astype(str) + df_grouped['month'].apply(lambda x:
f'{x:02d}')

df_grouped.drop(columns=['year', 'month'], inplace=True)

df_grouped = df_grouped[['sale_date', 'grand_total']]
```

```

df_grouped.to_csv(output_file, index=False)

file_path2 = '/penv/datana/datana/datasets/ptc/table_invoice_iqr.csv'

output_file2 = '/penv/datana/datana/datasets/ptc/table_invoice_fe.csv'

df2 = pd.read_csv(file_path2)

df_filtered2 = df2[['invoice_date', 'Col_8']]

df_filtered2.rename(columns={'Col_8': 'grand_total'}, inplace=True)

df_filtered2['invoice_date'] = pd.to_datetime(df_filtered2['invoice_date'])

df_filtered2['month'] = df_filtered2['invoice_date'].dt.month

df_filtered2['year'] = df_filtered2['invoice_date'].dt.year

df_grouped2 = df_filtered2.groupby(['year', 'month'])['grand_total'].sum().reset_index()

df_grouped2['invoice_date'] = df_grouped2['year'].astype(str) +
df_grouped2['month'].apply(lambda x: f'{x:02d}')

df_grouped2.drop(columns=['year', 'month'], inplace=True)

df_grouped2 = df_grouped2[['invoice_date', 'grand_total']]

df_grouped2.to_csv(output_file2, index=False)

```

```

root@ip-172-31-25-26: /penv/datana/datana/datasets/ptc
GNU nano 7.2      table invoice fe.csv
invoice_date,grand_total
202208,4246.5
202209,26761.0
202210,30540.245
202211,26162.04
202212,29671.44
202301,24355.0
202302,23855.53
202303,26895.95
202304,25163.75
202305,26435.71
202306,24157.605

```

Figure 12. Frequency Encoding result in 'table_invoice_fe.csv' dataset


```
GNU nano 7.2 table_sale_fe.csv
sale_date,grand_total
202311,2516.0
202312,3050.0
202401,11995.0
202402,13045.0
202403,14085.0
202404,17063.0
202405,17063.0
202406,14738.0
202407,18103.0
202408,22423.0
202409,23463.0
202410,28153.0
```

Figure 13. Frequency Encoding result in 'table_sale_fe.csv' dataset


```
GNU nano 7.2 starts.sh *
done
#PTC Workshop Database
ptc_tables=("table_attendance" "table_car" "table_invoice" "table_invoice_detail")
ptc_mysql_host="jdbc:mysql://sql12.freemysqlhosting.net/sql12744702"
ptc_mysql_user="sql12744702"
ptc_mysql_password="Jr12QFBUTg"
for ptc_table in "${ptc_tables[@]}; do
    hadoop fs -rm -r -f "/ptc/$ptc_table"
    sqoop import --connect "$ptc_mysql_host" --username "$ptc_mysql_user" --password "$ptc_mysql_password" --table "$ptc_table" --target-dir "/ptc/$ptc_table" --fields-terminated-by '\t'
    hadoop fs -getmerge "/ptc/$ptc_table" "/penv/datana/datana/datasets/ptc/$ptc_table"
done
#Activate Viruta Environment
cd /penv/denv/bin
source activate

#Data Preprocessing
/penv/remove_mission.py
/penv/remove_outliers.py
/penv/date_processing.py
/penv/frequncy_encoding.py

#Start Django
cd /penv/datana/
python3 manage.py runserver 0.0.0.0:8000
```

Figure 14. Add startup running files to 'starts.sh' file

4.3. Model Selection and Justification

Regression analysis is a technique for predictive modeling that measures the correlation between variables. This modeling is used as a tool to predict values in numeric type based on a variety of inputs. The relationship between an independent and dependent variable can be used to predict how the dependent variable changes follow with its independent counterpart. There are many types of regression models, including Simple Regression, Multiple Regression, Linear

Regression, Multiple Linear Regression, and Logistic Regression. Simple Regression predicts the relationship between a variable that is called dependent variable and another one is called independent variable. The Multiple Linear Regression shows that the direct or linear correlation between variables is possible. Linear regression is suitable for this problem because it allows us to predict a continuous target variable (sale or invoice income) based on historical data and trends. This model is especially useful when there is a linear relationship between the target variable and the predictor variables, as anticipated in this case. For this analysis, Linear Regression is chosen, as it aligns with the focused title of the report.

There are 3 types of Model Justification, including Interpretability, Scalability, and Efficiency. Interpretability means linear regression provides a straightforward interpretation, which allows the company's owner to understand how different factors contribute to the predicted income. Scalability refers to linear regression that can handle a large volume of data, which aligns with the scope of this project, where data from multiple periods and categories need to be analyzed. Additionally, it can be quickly retrained with new data, allowing the model to stay updated. The efficiency of linear regression is computationally efficient and can be implemented within the available AWS infrastructure, leveraging Hadoop and Django for seamless data flow and integration.

4.4. Model Development

File name : “/penv/datana/datana/views.py”

```
def workshop_regression_view(request):  
  
    # Path to the CSV file  
  
    csv_path = '/penv/datana/datana/datasets/ptc/table_invoice_fe.csv'  
  
    data = pd.read_csv(csv_path)  
  
    data['invoice_date'] = data['invoice_date'].astype(int)  
  
    X = data[['invoice_date']]
```

```

y = data['grand_total']

X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)

models = {

    'LinearRegression': LinearRegression(),

    'Ridge': Ridge(alpha=1.0),

    'Lasso': Lasso(alpha=0.1)

}

results = []

for model_name, model in models.items():

    model.fit(X_train, y_train)

    y_pred = model.predict(X_test)

    r2 = r2_score(y_test, y_pred)

    mse = mean_squared_error(y_test, y_pred)

    intercept = float(model.intercept_)

    coefficients = model.coef_.tolist()

    results.append({

        'model': model_name,

        'r2_score': round(r2, 2),

        'mean_squared_error': round(mse, 2),

        'intercept': round(intercept, 2),

```

```

        'coefficients': [round(c, 2) for c in coefficients]

    })

best_model = max(results, key=lambda x: x['r2_score'])

best_model_name = best_model['model']

cross_val_model = models[best_model_name]

cross_val_scores = cross_val_score(cross_val_model, X, y, cv=5, scoring='r2')

cross_val_mean = round(np.mean(cross_val_scores), 2)

cross_val_std = round(np.std(cross_val_scores), 2)

context = {

    'results': results,

    'best_model': best_model_name,

    'cross_val_r2': f"{cross_val_mean} ± {cross_val_std}"

}

return render(request, 'workshop_regression.html', context)

```

workshop_regression.html

```
<table class="table table-striped">
```

```
    <thead>
```

```
        <tr>
```

```
            <th>Model</th>
```

```
            <th>R-squared</th>
```

```

    <th>Mean Squared Error</th>

    <th>Intercept</th>

    <th>Coefficients</th>

</tr>

</thead>

<tbody>

    {% for result in results %}

    <tr>

        <td>{{ result.model }}</td>

        <td>{{ result.r2_score }}</td>

        <td>{{ result.mean_squared_error }}</td>

        <td>{{ result.intercept }}</td>

        <td>{{ result.coefficients }}</td>

    </tr>

    {% endfor %}

</tbody>

</table>

<hr>

<!-- Best Model -->

<h2>Best Model: {{ best_model }}</h2>

```

<p>Cross-validated R-squared: {{ cross_val_r2 }}</p>

</div>

Model	R-squared	Mean Squared Error	Intercept	Coefficients
LinearRegression	-0.42	96988534.23	5128129.32	[-25.22]
Ridge	-0.42	96988308.85	5128084.51	[-25.22]
Lasso	-0.42	96988514.57	5128125.41	[-25.22]

Best Model: LinearRegression
Cross-validated R-squared: -0.47 ± 0.41

Figure 15. Regression result of PTC Workshop displays on Django webpage.

Filename: : “/penv/datana/datana/views.py”

```
def computer_regression_view(request):
```

```
    csv_path = '/penv/datana/datana/datasets/pos/table_sale_fe.csv'
```

```
    data = pd.read_csv(csv_path)
```

```
    data['sale_date'] = data['sale_date'].astype(int)
```

```
    X = data[['sale_date']]
```

```
    y = data['grand_total']
```

```
    X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
```

```
    models = {
```

```
        'LinearRegression': LinearRegression(),
```

```
        'Ridge': Ridge(alpha=1.0),
```

```
        'Lasso': Lasso(alpha=0.1)
```

```

}

results = []

for model_name, model in models.items():

    model.fit(X_train, y_train)

    y_pred = model.predict(X_test)

    r2 = r2_score(y_test, y_pred)

    mse = mean_squared_error(y_test, y_pred)

    intercept = float(model.intercept_)

    coefficients = model.coef_.tolist()

    results.append({

        'model': model_name,

        'r2_score': round(r2, 2),

        'mean_squared_error': round(mse, 2),

        'intercept': round(intercept, 2),

        'coefficients': [round(c, 2) for c in coefficients]

    })

best_model = max(results, key=lambda x: x['r2_score'])

best_model_name = best_model['model']

cross_val_model = models[best_model_name]

cross_val_scores = cross_val_score(cross_val_model, X, y, cv=5, scoring='r2')

```

```

cross_val_mean = round(np.mean(cross_val_scores), 2)

cross_val_std = round(np.std(cross_val_scores), 2)

context = {

    'results': results,

    'best_model': best_model_name,

    'cross_val_r2': f"{cross_val_mean} ± {cross_val_std}"

}

return render(request, 'computer_regression.html', context)

```

computer_regression.html

```

<table class="table table-striped">

    <thead>

        <tr>

            <th>Model</th>

            <th>R-squared</th>

            <th>Mean Squared Error</th>

            <th>Intercept</th>

            <th>Coefficients</th>

        </tr>

    </thead>

    <tbody>

```

```

{% for result in results %}
<tr>
  <td>{{ result.model }}</td>
  <td>{{ result.r2_score }}</td>
  <td>{{ result.mean_squared_error }}</td>
  <td>{{ result.intercept }}</td>
  <td>{{ result.coefficients }}</td>
</tr>
{% endfor %}
</tbody>
</table>

<hr>

<!-- Best Model -->

<h2>Best Model: {{ best_model }}</h2>

<p>Cross-validated R-squared: {{ cross_val_r2 }}</p>

</div>

```

The screenshot shows a Django webpage titled "RACHNA Computer / Sale Regression". The page features a navigation menu on the left with links for "RACHNA Home", "Sale Statistic", "Sale Regression", "Sale Prediction", "Categories", "Customers", "Products", and "Sales". The main content area displays a table with the following data:

Model	R-squared	Mean Squared Error	Intercept	Coefficients
LinearRegression	0.78	20050563.37	-32156181.8	[158.95]
Ridge	0.78	20052076.27	-32152007.61	[158.93]
Lasso	0.78	20050571.93	-32156158.16	[158.95]

Below the table, the page indicates "Best Model: LinearRegression" and "Cross-validated R-squared: -147.71 ± 281.8".

Figure 16. Regression result of RACHNA Computer displays on Django webpage.

4.4.1. Hypermeter Tuning and Evaluation of Model Performance

Based on GeeksforGeeks (2023), “In the context of machine learning, hyperparameters are configuration variables that are set before the training process of a model begins. They control the learning process itself, rather than being learned from the data.” Before defining Hypermeter Tuning, the function in Django’s model begins by importing important libraries, loading the dataset from ‘../ptc/table_sale_fe.csv’, and defining the feature and target variables for the regression task. In this case, ‘sale_date’ column serves as the independent variable (feature), and ‘grand_total’ column is the dependent variable (target) to be predicted. The dataset is then split into training (80%) and testing (20%) sets using the train_test_split() function, ensuring consistency with random_state=42 for reproducibility. The code sets up three models: standard linear regression, ridge regression, and lasso regression. These models help explore different approaches to regularizing and improving the linear regression model.

```
csv_path = '/penv/datana/datana/datasets/pos/table_sale_fe.csv'

data = pd.read_csv(csv_path)

data['sale_date'] = data['sale_date'].astype(int)

X = data[['sale_date']]

y = data['grand_total']

X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)

models = {

    'LinearRegression': LinearRegression(),

    'Ridge': Ridge(alpha=1.0),

    'Lasso': Lasso(alpha=0.1)

}
```

In the Hyperparameter Tuning, the alpha parameter has been tuned for Ridge and Lasso regression models. To set hyperparameters for Ridge and Lasso, the model defines the alpha

parameter, which will be adjusted for both models. The higher the alpha ensures a stronger the regularization effect and helps to prevent overfitting by penalizing larger coefficients in the model. In the Fit Models and Tune Hyperparameters, a loop iterates over the models with direct training using the fit() function. The performance is evaluated using the R-squared metric (scoring='r2'). And the best model is selected and stored in the 'best_model' dictionary.

Each model in 'best_model' is tested by predicting target values using the test set (X_test). Then, performance metrics like R-squared (r2_score) and Mean Squared Error (mean_squared_error) are calculated by comparing the predicted values (y_pred) with the actual values (y_test). All these performance metrics for each model are displayed on the output screen. Another important evaluation, cross-validation is performed on the Best Model, identified by the highest R-squared score on the test set, and using the cross_val_score() function, a 5-fold cross-validation is applied to the entire dataset, calculating R-squared for each fold. The mean and standard deviation of these scores are then calculated and displayed to provide an estimate of the model's generalization ability.

```
csv_path = '/penv/datana/datana/datasets/pos/table_sale_fe.csv'

data = pd.read_csv(csv_path)

data['sale_date'] = data['sale_date'].astype(int)

X = data[['sale_date']]

y = data['grand_total']

X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)

models = {

    'LinearRegression': LinearRegression(),

    'Ridge': Ridge(alpha=1.0),

    'Lasso': Lasso(alpha=0.1)
```

```

}

results = []

for model_name, model in models.items():

    model.fit(X_train, y_train)

    y_pred = model.predict(X_test)

    r2 = r2_score(y_test, y_pred)

    mse = mean_squared_error(y_test, y_pred)

    intercept = float(model.intercept_)

    coefficients = model.coef_.tolist()

    results.append({

        'model': model_name,

        'r2_score': round(r2, 2),

        'mean_squared_error': round(mse, 2),

        'intercept': round(intercept, 2),

        'coefficients': [round(c, 2) for c in coefficients]

    })

best_model = max(results, key=lambda x: x['r2_score'])

best_model_name = best_model['model']

cross_val_model = models[best_model_name]

cross_val_scores = cross_val_score(cross_val_model, X, y, cv=5, scoring='r2')

```

```

cross_val_mean = round(np.mean(cross_val_scores), 2)

cross_val_std = round(np.std(cross_val_scores), 2)

context = {

    'results': results,

    'best_model': best_model_name,

    'cross_val_r2': f"{cross_val_mean} ± {cross_val_std}"

}

return render(request, 'computer_regression.html', context)

```

4.4.2. Interpretation of Model Parameters and Results

Soman (2024) wrote on medium.com that, “Model interpretation refers to the process of understanding and explaining the behavior and decision-making process of a machine learning model.” It shifts the regression line up or down. Coefficients (slopes) represent the change in the target variable for a one-unit change in the corresponding input feature, holding all other features constant. The parameters of the Linear Regression Model, refer to the strength and direction of the relationship between each input feature and the target variable. The intercept or bias represents the predicted target value when all input features are zero essentially shifting the regression line up or down. The coefficients show how much the target variable changes with a one-unit increase in the corresponding feature, assuming all other features remain constant. A positive coefficient means the feature and target have a direct relationship, while a negative coefficient signals an inverse relationship. Both intercept and coefficients are essential for understanding the linear relationship between your features and target in a linear regression model. In a linear model, it shifts the lineup or down along the vertical axis (Y-axis). Positive coefficients indicate that as the input feature increases, the target variable increases. If the coefficient were negative, it would mean that as the input feature increases, the target variable decreases. So, it means that for every one-unit increase in the frequency feature, the predicted amount increases by approximately Intercept units.

4.5. Application of the Model

4.5.1. PTC Workshop Invoice's Sale Prediction

The linear regression model uses historical data to predict monthly income on 'table_invoice' of PTC Workshop's database. The model's predictions give awareness for the future income, enabling the company to make any decisions and identify opportunities for growth.

Figure 17. Sale prediction of PTC Workshop – part 1

Original Sales Data

Sale Date	Grand Total
202208	4246.5
202209	26761.0
202210	30540.245
202211	26162.04
202212	29671.44
202301	24355.0
202302	23855.53
202303	26895.95

Figure 18. Sale prediction of PTC Workshop – part 2

Extended Sales Data (Predicted for the next months)

Sale Date	Predicted Grand Total
202208	24692.52371188358
202209	24688.590284900507
202210	24684.65685791755
202211	24680.72343093448
202212	24676.790003951523
202301	24326.71500246378
202302	24322.78157548071

Figure 19. Sale prediction of PTC Workshop – part 3

Figure 20. Sale prediction of PTC Workshop – part 4

4.5.2. RACHNA Computer Sale Prediction

The model leverages product sales, category performance, and inventory turnover rates to predict income, helping RACHNA Computer anticipate revenue fluctuations. Based on the model's output, RACHNA Computer can make strategic decisions, such as stocking up on high-demand products or launching promotions for underperforming categories during slower periods. By employing linear regression, the project provides both companies with actionable insights into their future financial performance, grounded in data science and statistical modeling. This approach not only addresses immediate business concerns but also establishes a data-driven foundation for ongoing financial planning and operational optimization.

Figure 21. Sale prediction of RACHNA Computer – part 1

Original Sales Data

Sale Date	Grand Total
202311	2516
202312	3050
202401	11995

Figure 22. Sale prediction of RACHNA Computer – part 2

Extended Sales Data (Predicted for the next months)

Sale Date	Predicted Grand Total
202311	2077.931790046394
202312	2247.8702874183655
202401	17372.39655404538
202402	17542.3350514248
202403	17712.273548804224
202404	17882.212046183646

Figure 23. Sale prediction of RACHNA Computer – part 3

Figure 24. Sale prediction of RACHNA Computer – part 3

5. Results and Discussion

5.1. Results of Data Analysis and Model Performance

PTC Workshop: For all models such as Linear Regression, Ridge, and Lasso the R-squared value result is -0.42 means that they fail to explain the variance in the dependent variable (invoice income). The Mean Squared Error values for all models are: 96,985,534.23 for Linear Regression, 96,988,308.85 for Ridge, and 96,985,814.57 for Lasso. These values are quite high, suggesting that the model's predictions are far from the actual values on average. The small

differences between the MSE values indicate that the regularization techniques in Ridge and Lasso did not significantly improve performance over Linear Regression. The intercept values for all models are approximately 5,128,129, and the coefficient is -25.22. This suggests that the dependent variable decreases by 25.22 units for each unit increase in the independent variable. The cross-validated R-squared result is -0.47 with a standard deviation of 0.41, this indicates poor generalization performance. The model's predictions do not align well with actual values on unseen data.

RACHNA Computer: For all models such as LinearRegression, Ridge, and Lasso the R-squared value result is 0.78 means that 78% of the variance in the dependent variable (sale income) has been explained by the service 'sale_date' variable (independent variables). This is a good fit, meaning the models can capture the relationship between the variables fairly well. However, it also implies that 22% of the variance remains unexplained, which can be due to missing features or inherent noise in the data. The Mean Squared Error values for all models are: 20,050,563.37 for Linear Regression, 20,052,075.27 for Ridge, and 20,050,571.93 for Lasso. This indicates that the predictions of all three models are very similar and relatively close to the actual values. The small differences between MSE values suggest that the models are performing nearly identically, at least on the test data. While MSE values are similar, Ridge and Lasso may perform better on unseen data due to the regularization techniques they employ, which helping controlling overfitting by penalizing large coefficients. The cross-validated R-squared result is -147.71 with a standard deviation of 281.8, which means it is much lower than the original R-squared value of 0.78. A negative R-squared in cross-validation indicates poor generalization performance. This drop means that the models are overfitting to the training data and it performs well on the test set but struggling to generalize to new unseen data.

5.2. Implications of the Results

PTC Workshop: The poor performance of the models suggests that 'sale_date' alone is not a strong predictor of 'grand_total'. This might be due to the influence of other unaccounted factors. The negative relationship observed between 'sale_date' and 'grand_total' could indicate a trend that is specific to the dataset but may not be reflective of broader sales behavior.

Therefore, it is critical for the company to explore additional variables and perform feature engineering to improve model accuracy.

RACHNA Computer: The relatively high R-squared value indicates a better fit, suggesting that `sale_date` is a reasonable predictor of `grand_total` for this company. However, the drop in performance during cross-validation highlights a potential overfitting issue. This means that while the model may work well on historical data, its performance on unseen data could be significantly worse. The business should consider introducing additional features or applying more robust regularization techniques to mitigate overfitting and improve generalization.

5.3. Recommendations for Further Research

Feature Engineering: For both companies, expanding the feature set to include additional factors could provide valuable insights and improve model performance. For example, including holidays or special sales periods as binary features could help capture the spikes in sales often seen during those times.

Time Series Analysis: Since the `'sale_date'` variable is time-dependent, applying time series forecasting methods could provide more accurate predictions by accounting for temporal patterns and trends. These models are specifically designed to handle the time-based nature of the data and could outperform linear models in capturing underlying patterns.

Model Regularization: While Ridge and Lasso regression helped control overfitting, more advanced techniques. ElasticNet is a linear regression model that combines both L1 and L2 regularization, offering a balance between the strengths of Ridge and Lasso. This could further help in improving generalization, especially for datasets with many features or collinearity.

Cross-Validation and Hyperparameter Tuning: While cross-validation was applied, additional hyperparameter tuning using techniques like Grid Search or Random Search could improve the model's performance by finding the optimal values for the regularization parameters (e.g., α in Ridge and Lasso regression). This process could also help address issues of overfitting.

6. Implementation and Deployment

In figure 22 is the Architectural Diagram for the System Deployed of the project on AWS integrating multiple components to handle data processing and scaling of web-based applications.

Figure 25. Architectural Diagram for the System Deployed on AWS

6.1. Implementation and Deployment Process

6.1.1. Create EC2 Instance

Before designing and implementing a distributed cloud-based system that can perform a large-scale data processing task, an AWS account is needed to create and sign in to the AWS management console webpage. After completing registration with AWS and log in the AWS management console creates a first EC2 instance with the following information:

- **Name:** Server01
- **Application Machine Image:** Ubuntu
- **Key pair name:** Create new key pair (Server01.ppk)

Figure 26. Server01 Instance Information

- **Instance type:** t2.medium instead of t2.micro because Apache Hadoop need more performance and free space to perform data processing from remote databases.

Current instance type

t2.medium

New instance type

EBS-optimized
EBS-optimized is not supported for this instance type

▼ Instance type comparison

Attribute	t2.medium
On-Demand Linux pricing	0.0584 USD per Hour
On-Demand Windows pricing	0.0764 USD per Hour
vCPUs	2 (2 core)
Memory (MiB)	4096
Storage (GB)	-
Supported root device types	ebs
Network performance	Low to Moderate
Architecture	i386
Burstable	true
Free-tier eligible	false
Current generation	true

[Compare more instance type attributes](#)

Figure 27. t2.medium instance type information

- **Firewall:** Create security group to allow HTTP (80), SSH (22), Custom TCP for Apache Hadoop (54310) and Django (8000) in Inbound rules names launch-wizard-1

Figure 28. Editing inbound rules

- **Configure storage:** Add new volume (EBS volume 10GB) for external connecting to Django project source code and datasets to analyze from remote databases.

Figure 29. Adding EBS volume

6.1.2. Remote to AWS EC2 Instance

After completed creating an EC2 Instance, next is remotng from local computer to cloud instance for management by using Public DNS, username and provided private key.

Figure 30. SSH client information

Private key has been downloaded while create an AWS EC2 Instance to local hard drive of local computer. For local computer, there are many applications to use and PuTTY is a free, open-source terminal emulator and SSH (Secure Shell) client that allows users to connect to remote servers, typically Unix-like systems (Linux, macOS), from a Windows machine.

Figure 31. Remoting to EC2 by using PuTTY

After remoting to EC2 instance, now it can be managed by using PuTTY on local computer.


```
ubuntu@ip-172-31-25-26: ~
* Support: https://ubuntu.com/pro

System information as of Wed Nov 13 16:14:33 UTC 2024

System load: 0.25          Processes:          118
Usage of /: 56.9% of 6.71GB  Users logged in: 0
Memory usage: 5%          IPv4 address for enX0: 172.31.25.26
Swap usage: 0%

* Ubuntu Pro delivers the most comprehensive open source security and
  compliance features.

https://ubuntu.com/aws/pro

Expanded Security Maintenance for Applications is not enabled.

0 updates can be applied immediately.

Enable ESM Apps to receive additional future security updates.
See https://ubuntu.com/esm or run: sudo pro status

Last login: Wed Nov 13 13:37:41 2024 from 175.100.10.7
ubuntu@ip-172-31-25-26:~$
```

Figure 32. Connecting to EC2 Instance on PuTTY

6.1.3. Java and Apache Hadoop Installation

Apache Hadoop is run based on Java, so after install Java, it needed to be verified by checking the following commands:

java -version

javac -version


```
root@ip-172-31-25-26: /
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/# java -version
openjdk version "1.8.0_432"
OpenJDK Runtime Environment (build 1.8.0_432-8u432-ga~us1-0ubuntu2~24.04-ga)
OpenJDK 64-Bit Server VM (build 25.432-bga, mixed mode)
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/# javac -version
javac 1.8.0_432
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/#
```

Figure 33. Displaying Java version

And JAVA_HOME path is also need to add in environment as the following commands:

nano /etc/environment

source /etc/environment


```
root@ip-172-31-25-26: /
GNU nano 7.2 /etc/environment
PATH="/usr/local/sbin:/usr/local/bin:/usr/sbin:/usr/bin:/sbin:/bin:/usr/games:/>
JAVA_HOME="/usr/lib/jvm/java-8-openjdk-amd64/"
```

Figure 34. Adding Java path to environment

Hadoop relies heavily on SSH (Secure Shell) for communication between nodes in the cluster, such as between the NameNode, DataNodes, ResourceManager, and NodeManagers. SSH allows these nodes to communicate securely over the network with the following commands:

apt-get openssh-server

ssh-keygen -t rsa -P ""

cat \$HOME/.ssh/id_rsa.pub >> \$HOME/.ssh/authorized_keys

There are many files to edit or add more information with nano editor while installing Apache Hadoop such as:

nano /usr/local/hadoop/etc/hadoop/hadoop-env.sh

nano /usr/local/hadoop/etc/hadoop/hdfs-site.xml

nano /usr/local/hadoop/etc/hadoop/mapred-site.xml

nano /usr/local/hadoop/etc/hadoop/yarn-site.xml

```
root@ip-172-31-25-26: /home/ubuntu
GNU nano 7.2 /root/.bashrc
# sources /etc/bash.bashrc).
#if [ -f /etc/bash_completion ] && ! shopt -oq posix; then
#   . /etc/bash_completion
#fi

#HADOOP VARIABLES START
export JAVA_HOME=/usr/lib/jvm/java-8-openjdk-amd64

export HADOOP_INSTALL=/usr/local/hadoop
export PATH=$PATH:$HADOOP_INSTALL/bin
export PATH=$PATH:$HADOOP_INSTALL/sbin
export HADOOP_MAPRED_HOME=$HADOOP_INSTALL
export HADOOP_COMMON_HOME=$HADOOP_INSTALL
export HADOOP_HDFS_HOME=$HADOOP_INSTALL
export YARN_HOME=$HADOOP_INSTALL
export HADOOP_COMMON_LIB_NATIVE_DIR=$HADOOP_INSTALL/lib/native
export HADOOP_OPTS="-Djava.library.path=$HADOOP_INSTALL/lib"
export HADOOP_PREFIX=$HADOOP_INSTALL
export HADOOP_CONF_DIR=$HADOOP_PREFIX/etc/hadoop
#HADOOP END

^G Help      ^O Write Out ^W Where Is  ^K Cut       ^T Execute  ^C Location
^X Exit      ^R Read File ^\ Replace   ^U Paste     ^J Justify  ^_ Go To Line
```

Figure 35. Adding Hadoop paths to ‘.bashrc’

```
root@ip-172-31-25-26: /home/ubuntu
GNU nano 7.2 /usr/local/hadoop/etc/hadoop/hdfs-site.xml
-->
<!-- Put site-specific property overrides in this file. -->

<configuration>
<property>
<name>dfs.replication</name>
<value>1</value>
<description>Default block replication.</description>
</property>
<property>
<name>dfs.permissions</name>
<value>>false</value>
</property>
<property>
<name>dfs.datanode.data.dir</name>
<value>file:/usr/local/hadoop_store/hdfs/datanode</value>
</property>
<property>
<name>dfs.webhdfs.enabled</name>
<value>>true</value>
</property>
<property>
  <name>dfs.namenode.rpc-address</name>
  <value>localhost:54310</value>
</property>
</configuration>
```

Figure 36. Adding configuration information to ‘hdfs-site.xml’

```
root@ip-172-31-25-26: /home/ubuntu
GNU nano 7.2 /usr/local/hadoop/etc/hadoop/core-site.xml
<?xml-stylesheet type="text/xsl" href="configuration.xsl"?>
<!--
Licensed under the Apache License, Version 2.0 (the "License");
you may not use this file except in compliance with the License.
You may obtain a copy of the License at

    http://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0

Unless required by applicable law or agreed to in writing, software
distributed under the License is distributed on an "AS IS" BASIS,
WITHOUT WARRANTIES OR CONDITIONS OF ANY KIND, either express or implied.
See the License for the specific language governing permissions and
limitations under the License. See accompanying LICENSE file.
-->

<!-- Put site-specific property overrides in this file. -->

<configuration>
<property>
<name>hadoop.tmp.dir</name>
<value>/app/hadoop/tmp</value>
<description>A base for other temporary directories.</description>
</property>
<property>
<name>fs.defaultFS</name>
<value>hdfs://localhost:54310</value>
<description>The name</description>
</property>
</configuration>
```

Figure 37. Adding configuration information to ‘core-site.xml’

```
root@ip-172-31-25-26: /home/ubuntu
GNU nano 7.2 /usr/local/hadoop/etc/hadoop/mapred-site.xml
<?xml version="1.0"?>
<?xml-stylesheet type="text/xsl" href="configuration.xsl"?>
<!--
Licensed under the Apache License, Version 2.0 (the "License");
you may not use this file except in compliance with the License.
You may obtain a copy of the License at

    http://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0

Unless required by applicable law or agreed to in writing, software
distributed under the License is distributed on an "AS IS" BASIS,
WITHOUT WARRANTIES OR CONDITIONS OF ANY KIND, either express or implied.
See the License for the specific language governing permissions and
limitations under the License. See accompanying LICENSE file.
-->

<!-- Put site-specific property overrides in this file. -->

<configuration>
<property>
<name>mapreduce.framework.name</name>
<value>yarn</value>
</property>
</configuration>
```

Figure 38. Adding configuration information to ‘mapred-site.xml’

```
root@ip-172-31-25-26: /home/ubuntu
GNU nano 7.2 /usr/local/hadoop/etc/hadoop/yarn-site.xml
<?xml version="1.0"?>
<!--
Licensed under the Apache License, Version 2.0 (the "License");
you may not use this file except in compliance with the License.
You may obtain a copy of the License at

    http://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0

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distributed under the License is distributed on an "AS IS" BASIS,
WITHOUT WARRANTIES OR CONDITIONS OF ANY KIND, either express or implied.
See the License for the specific language governing permissions and
limitations under the License. See accompanying LICENSE file.
-->
<configuration>

<!-- Site specific YARN configuration properties -->
<property>
<name>yarn.nodemanager.aux-services</name>
<value>mapreduce_shuffle</value>
</property>
<property>
<name>yarn.nodemanager.auxservices.mapreduce.shuffle.class</name>
<value>org.apache.hadoop.mapred.ShuffleHandler</value>
</property>
</configuration>
```

Figure 39. Adding configuration information to 'yarn-site.xml'

```
root@ip-172-31-25-26: /
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/# hadoop version
Hadoop 2.7.3
Subversion https://git-wip-us.apache.org/repos/asf/hadoop.git -r baa91f7c6bc9cb92be5982de4719c1c8af91ccff
Compiled by root on 2016-08-18T01:41Z
Compiled with protoc 2.5.0
From source with checksum 2e4ce5f957ea4db193bce3734ff29ff4
This command was run using /usr/local/hadoop/share/hadoop/common/hadoop-common-2.7.3.jar
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/# █
```

Figure 40. Checking Hadoop version

=> ./start-all.sh

Apache Hadoop and its services are running by using the following commands:

cd /usr/local/hadoop/sbin/

./start-all.sh

jps

```
root@ip-172-31-25-26: /usr/local/hadoop/sbin
root@ip-172-31-25-26:~# cd /usr/local/hadoop/sbin/
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/usr/local/hadoop/sbin# ./start-all.sh
This script is Deprecated. Instead use start-dfs.sh and start-yarn.sh
24/11/13 16:30:12 WARN util.NativeCodeLoader: Unable to load native-hadoop library for your platform... using builtin-java classes where applicable
Starting namenodes on [localhost]
localhost: starting namenode, logging to /usr/local/hadoop/logs/hadoop-root-namenode-ip-172-31-25-26.out
localhost: starting datanode, logging to /usr/local/hadoop/logs/hadoop-root-datanode-ip-172-31-25-26.out
Starting secondary namenodes [0.0.0.0]
0.0.0.0: starting secondarynamenode, logging to /usr/local/hadoop/logs/hadoop-root-secondarynamenode-ip-172-31-25-26.out
24/11/13 16:30:28 WARN util.NativeCodeLoader: Unable to load native-hadoop library for your platform... using builtin-java classes where applicable
starting yarn daemons
starting resourcemanager, logging to /usr/local/hadoop/logs/yarn-root-resourcemanager-ip-172-31-25-26.out
localhost: starting nodemanager, logging to /usr/local/hadoop/logs/yarn-root-nodemanager-ip-172-31-25-26.out
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/usr/local/hadoop/sbin# jps
5922 SecondaryNameNode
5730 DataNode
5575 NameNode
6057 ResourceManager
6493 Jps
6191 NodeManager
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/usr/local/hadoop/sbin#
```

Figure 41. Using the 'jps' command

6.1.4. Sqoop Installation

While installing Apache Sqoop, some files are also needed to edit with nano editor including:

nano ~/.bashrc

nano /usr/local/sqoop/conf/sqoop-env.sh

```
root@ip-172-31-25-26: /home/ubuntu
GNU nano 7.2 /root/.bashrc
#HADOOP VARIABLES START
export JAVA_HOME=/usr/lib/jvm/java-8-openjdk-amd64

export HADOOP_INSTALL=/usr/local/hadoop
export PATH=$PATH:$HADOOP_INSTALL/bin
export PATH=$PATH:$HADOOP_INSTALL/sbin
export HADOOP_MAPRED_HOME=$HADOOP_INSTALL
export HADOOP_COMMON_HOME=$HADOOP_INSTALL
export HADOOP_HDFS_HOME=$HADOOP_INSTALL
export YARN_HOME=$HADOOP_INSTALL
export HADOOP_COMMON_LIB_NATIVE_DIR=$HADOOP_INSTALL/lib/native
export HADOOP_OPTS="-Djava.library.path=$HADOOP_INSTALL/lib"
export HADOOP_PREFIX=$HADOOP_INSTALL
export HADOOP_CONF_DIR=$HADOOP_PREFIX/etc/hadoop
#HADOOP END

export SQOOP_HOME=/usr/local/sqoop
export PATH=$PATH:$SQOOP_HOME/bin
```

Figure 42. Adding Sqoop Home Path to '.bashrc'

```
root@ip-172-31-25-26: /home/ubuntu
GNU nano 7.2 /usr/local/sqoop/conf/sqoop-env.sh
#
# Unless required by applicable law or agreed to in writing, software
# distributed under the License is distributed on an "AS IS" BASIS,
# WITHOUT WARRANTIES OR CONDITIONS OF ANY KIND, either express or implied.
# See the License for the specific language governing permissions and
# limitations under the License.
#
# included in all the hadoop scripts with source command
# should not be executable directly
# also should not be passed any arguments, since we need original $*
#
# Set Hadoop-specific environment variables here.
#
#Set path to where bin/hadoop is available
#export HADOOP_COMMON_HOME=
#
#Set path to where hadoop-*-core.jar is available
#export HADOOP_MAPRED_HOME=
#
#set the path to where bin/hbase is available
#export HBASE_HOME=
#
#Set the path to where bin/hive is available
#export HIVE_HOME=
#
#Set the path for where zookeeper config dir is
#export ZOO_CFG_DIR=
export HADOOP_COMMON_HOME=/usr/local/hadoop
export HADOOP_MAPRED_HOME=/usr/local/hadoop
```

Figure 43. Editing sqoop-env.sh

The 'sqoop version' is used to verify completed installation and is used to check version of Sqoop.

```
root@ip-172-31-25-26: /
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/# sqoop version
Warning: /usr/local/sqoop/./hbase does not exist! HBase imports will fail.
Please set $HBASE_HOME to the root of your HBase installation.
Warning: /usr/local/sqoop/./hcatalog does not exist! HCatalog jobs will fail.
Please set $HCAT_HOME to the root of your HCatalog installation.
Warning: /usr/local/sqoop/./accumulo does not exist! Accumulo imports will fail.
Please set $ACCUMULO_HOME to the root of your Accumulo installation.
Warning: /usr/local/sqoop/./zookeeper does not exist! Accumulo imports will fail.
Please set $ZOOKEEPER_HOME to the root of your Zookeeper installation.
24/11/13 05:44:52 INFO sqoop.Sqoop: Running Sqoop version: 1.4.7
Sqoop 1.4.7
git commit id 2328971411f57f0cb683dfb79d19d4d19d185dd8
Compiled by maugli on Thu Dec 21 15:59:58 STD 2017
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/# █
```

Figure 44. Checking Sqoop Version

6.1.5. EBS Mounting

EBS is the one of another choice to perform data processing task. While create the first instance, EBS was also added with 10 GiB storage. So, this performance is attaching and mounting first EBS with first EC2 instance. For first part, the 'lsblk' command is used to list all block devices and verify which new volume is attached. As the result, new EBS volume is 'xvdb'. /xvdb'. Then 'mkfs -t ext4 /dev command is used to format this volume before adding to instance permantly.

```
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/# lsblk
NAME        MAJ:MIN RM  SIZE RO TYPE MOUNTPOINTS
loop0        7:0    0 25.2M  1 loop /snap/amazon-ssm-agent/7993
loop1        7:1    0 55.7M  1 loop /snap/core18/2829
loop2        7:2    0 55.4M  1 loop /snap/core18/2846
loop3        7:3    0 38.8M  1 loop /snap/snapd/21759
xvda        202:0    0   8G  0 disk
├─xvda1     202:1    0   7G  0 part /
├─xvda14   202:14    0   4M  0 part
├─xvda15   202:15    0 106M  0 part /boot/efi
└─xvda16   259:0    0  913M  0 part /boot
xvdb        202:16    0  10G  0 disk
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/# mkfs -t ext4 /dev/xvdb
mke2fs 1.47.0 (5-Feb-2023)
Creating filesystem with 2621440 4k blocks and 655360 inodes
Filesystem UUID: 587e14bc-c84d-4c3e-a6f0-5cd4f195568d
Superblock backups stored on blocks:
    32768, 98304, 163840, 229376, 294912, 819200, 884736, 1605632
```

Figure 45. Formatting EBS volume

The 'blkid /dev/xvdb' command is used to show UUID of the new EBS volume. The 'vi /etc/fstab' is used to add EBS volume to the first EC2 instance permanently. After completing, the new EBS volume has been attached to EC2 instance and mount to the virtual environment directory location of Django project is '/penv'.


```
root@ip-172-31-25-26: /
LABEL=cloudimg-rootfs / ext4 discard,commit=30,errors=remount-ro
0 1
LABEL=BOOT /boot ext4 defaults 0 2
LABEL=UEFI /boot/efi vfat umask=0077 0 1

UUID="587e14bc-c84d-4c3e-a6f0-5cd4f195568d" /penv ext4 defaults,nofail 0 2
```

Figure 46. Mounting EBS volume permanently

The 'df -hT' can be used again to verify the EBS attachment and mounting information.


```
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/penv# df -hT
Filesystem      Type      Size      Used      Avail     Use%      Mounted on
/dev/root       ext4      6.8G      3.9G      2.9G      57%       /
tmpfs           tmpfs     2.0G      0          2.0G      0%        /dev/shm
tmpfs           tmpfs     783M      884K      782M      1%        /run
tmpfs           tmpfs     5.0M      0          5.0M      0%        /run/lock
/dev/xvda16     ext4      881M      133M      687M      17%       /boot
/dev/xvda15     vfat      105M      6.1M      99M       6%        /boot/efi
tmpfs           tmpfs     392M      16K       392M      1%        /run/user/1000
/dev/xvdb       ext4      9.8G      16M       9.3G      1%        /penv
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/penv#
```

Figure 47. Checking mounted partition information

6.1.6. Python and Django Installation

There are many ways or commands to install Python, for example 'sudo apt install python3'. After completed installation, 'python3 -V' is used to check its version.

```
root@ip-172-31-25-26: ~  
root@ip-172-31-25-26:~# python3 -V  
Python 3.12.3  
root@ip-172-31-25-26:~# █
```

Figure 48. Checking Python version

And after install virtual environment and Django, ‘tree’ command can be used to list all contents in Django project.

```
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/penv# tree /penv/datana/  
/penv/datana/  
├── __pycache__  
│   └── manage.cpython-312.pyc  
├── datana  
│   ├── __init__.py  
│   ├── __pycache__  
│   │   ├── __init__.cpython-312.pyc  
│   │   ├── settings.cpython-312.pyc  
│   │   ├── urls.cpython-312.pyc  
│   │   ├── views.cpython-312.pyc  
│   │   └── wsgi.cpython-312.pyc  
│   ├── asgi.py  
│   ├── settings.py  
│   ├── templates  
│   │   └── login.html  
│   ├── urls.py  
│   ├── views.py  
│   └── wsgi.py  
├── db.sqlite3  
└── manage.py
```

Figure 49. Listing Django project contents

After completed installation and Django application creating, the following command is used to run Django web based application.

```
cd /penv/datana
```

```
python3 manage.py runserver 0.0.0.0:8000
```

```
(p) root@ip-172-31-25-26:/penv/datana# python3 manage.py runserver 0.0.0.0:8000
Watching for file changes with StatReloader
Performing system checks...

System check identified no issues (0 silenced).
November 13, 2024 - 02:55:19
Django version 4.2.11, using settings 'datana.settings'
Starting development server at http://0.0.0.0:8000/
Quit the server with CONTROL-C.

[13/Nov/2024 02:55:24] "GET / HTTP/1.1" 200 10664
```

Figure 50. Running Django project

This address is used to see the result on the webpage, 'ec2-18-142-230-228.ap-southeast-1.compute.amazonaws.com:8000/login/'.

Figure 51. Accessing Login page of Django project

6.1.7. AMI Creating

After testing the web server, this step is creating an amazon machine image (AMI) of the first instance to save snapshot of the operating system and names it to 'Ubuntu01. Then create a second EC2 instance later by choosing this AMI.

Figure 52. Creating a AMI from current instance

So, by using saved AMI can make the Server02 (second EC2 instance) has OS, apps and services are same as the Server01 (first EC2 instance) such as updated OS, Apache Hadoop, Apache Sqoop, Django source codes and especially is EBS that is can be a second backup storage on second EC2 that is used to synchronize data from first EBS in first EC2 instance.

Figure 53. Creating Server02 Instance

But in setting.py in Django app must be change its Public DNS name is ec2-18-143-138-229.ap-southeast-1.compute.amazonaws.com because it is its own name, not the Server01.


```
root@ip-172-31-47-76: /penv/datana
GNU nano 7.2 datana/settings.py
# Build paths inside the project like this: BASE_DIR / 'subdir'.
BASE_DIR = Path(__file__).resolve().parent.parent

# Quick-start development settings - unsuitable for production
# See https://docs.djangoproject.com/en/4.2/howto/deployment/checklist/

# SECURITY WARNING: keep the secret key used in production secret!
SECRET_KEY = 'django-insecure-%-3)1w@2_mp51ihz&upb&vv7(o4sys9e-+!_tuw05t@0m9&4

# SECURITY WARNING: don't run with debug turned on in production!
DEBUG = True

ALLOWED_HOSTS = ['ec2-18-142-230-228.ap-southeast-1.compute.amazonaws.com']

# Application definition

INSTALLED_APPS = [
^G Help      ^O Write Out ^W Where Is  ^K Cut       ^T Execute  ^C Location
^X Exit      ^R Read File ^\ Replace   ^U Paste     ^J Justify  ^_ Go To Line
```

Figure 54. Change Allowed Hosts in setting.py of Django project

6.1.8. EBSs Synchronization

The 'rsync' command is used in crontab utility for data recovering from failure and continuing to function to synchronize data from Django project directory location (/penv/datana/) in Server01 (first EC2 instance) to Django project directory location (/penv/datana/) in Server02 (second EC2 instance). But before using this command, ensure that both EC2 instances have been set up SSH Key-Based authentication and proper permission correctly and then use 'crontab -e' command.


```
# For example, you can run a backup of all your user accounts
# at 5 a.m every week with:
# 0 5 * * 1 tar -zcf /var/backups/home.tgz /home/
#
# For more information see the manual pages of crontab(5) and cron(8)
#
# m h dom mon dow  command
*/1 * * * * rsync -avz /penv/ ubuntu@172.31.47.76:/penv/
```

Figure 55. Synchronizing web directory from Server01 to Server02

After completed the synchronization, every one-minute Django project directory in Server01 is always sync data to Server02.

```
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/penv# tree /penv/datana
/penv/datana
├── pycache
│   └── manage.cpython-312.pyc
├── datana
│   ├── __init__.py
│   ├── pycache
│   │   ├── __init__.cpython-312.pyc
│   │   ├── settings.cpython-312.pyc
│   │   ├── urls.cpython-312.pyc
│   │   ├── views.cpython-312.pyc
│   │   └── wsgi.cpython-312.pyc
│   ├── asgi.py
│   ├── settings.py
│   └── templates
│       └── login.html
├── urls.py
├── views.py
├── wsgi.py
├── db.sqlite3
└── manage.py

5 directories, 15 files
root@ip-172-31-25-26:/penv#

root@ip-172-31-47-76:/penv# tree /penv/datana
/penv/datana
├── pycache
│   └── manage.cpython-312.pyc
├── datana
│   ├── __init__.py
│   ├── pycache
│   │   ├── __init__.cpython-312.pyc
│   │   ├── settings.cpython-312.pyc
│   │   ├── urls.cpython-312.pyc
│   │   ├── views.cpython-312.pyc
│   │   └── wsgi.cpython-312.pyc
│   ├── asgi.py
│   ├── settings.py
│   └── templates
│       └── login.html
├── urls.py
├── views.py
├── wsgi.py
├── db.sqlite3
└── manage.py

5 directories, 15 files
root@ip-172-31-47-76:/penv#
```

Figure 56. Comparing synced data from Server01 to Server02

6.1.9. Application Load Balancing

Application Load Balancing (ALB) is used for service recovering from failure and continuing to function to redirect to active instance and change direction to another active instance if the current instance has been shut down accidentally. The follow information is used while creating an ALB:

- **Load Balance Name** : “ALB01”
- **Register targets** : “Server01 (first instance), Server02 (second instance)”
- **Availability Zones** : “ap-southeast-1b (apse1-az2)”
: “ap-southeast-1c (apse1-az3)”
: “ap-southeast-1a (apse1-az1)”

- **Security groups** : Create a New Security Group (launch-wizard-1), Inbound rule are HTTP (80), SSH (22), Custom TCP (8000), and Custom TCP (54310).

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Security group rule...	IP version	Type	Protocol	Port range	Source
<input type="checkbox"/>	-	sgr-0cb64f5b2a74f4125	IPv4	Custom TCP	TCP	8000	0.0.0.0/0
<input type="checkbox"/>	-	sgr-06fb1268b39299c3c	IPv4	HTTP	TCP	80	0.0.0.0/0
<input type="checkbox"/>	-	sgr-018bc3e0dbb43aa...	IPv4	SSH	TCP	22	0.0.0.0/0
<input type="checkbox"/>	-	sgr-025eafa1917bb15ae	IPv4	Custom TCP	TCP	54310	0.0.0.0/0

Figure 57. Adding Security Groups for ABL

- **Listeners and routing**: Create a target group (NTG)

<input type="checkbox"/>	Instance ID	Name	Port	Zone
<input type="checkbox"/>	i-0e0f525bbd4b9ce9b	Server02	8000	ap-southeast-...
<input type="checkbox"/>	i-0e0f525bbd4b9ce9b	Server02	80	ap-southeast-...
<input type="checkbox"/>	i-07f68533a20cf6113	Server01	80	ap-southeast-...
<input type="checkbox"/>	i-07f68533a20cf6113	Server01	8000	ap-southeast-...

Figure 58. Adding Registered Targets for ABL

After completing, a new ABL is displayed in the Load Balancers list.

Load balancers (1/1)
Elastic Load Balancing scales your load balancer capacity automatically in response to changes in incoming traffic.

Filter load balancers

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Name	DNS name	State	VPC ID
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ALB01	ALB01-1373741819.ap-so...	Active	vpc-0acc42217603159...

Figure 59. ABL List

To test the ALB, type its url in **http://alb01-1373741819.ap-southeast-1.elb.amazonaws.com:8000/login/**

Figure 60. Accessing Django project through ABL's URL

6.1.10. Auto Scaling Group

Auto Scaling Group (ASG) can recover from failures and continue to function without significant loss of service or processing power. There are 2 parts to implement ASG including creating template and creating ASG.

Creating of Launch Template:

- **Template name** : LT01
- **Template version description** : LT01
- **Application and OS Images** : Recently launched
- **Amazon Machine Image (AMI)** : “ubuntu/images/hvm-ssd-gp3/ubuntu-noble-24.04-amd64-server-20240927”
- **Instance Type** : t2.medium
- **Key pair name** : Server01
- **Network settings** : Create security group:

Create security group (launch-wizard-1)

: Inbound rules (HTTP, SSH)

- EBS Volumes

▼ Volume 2 (Custom)
Remove

Storage type Info EBS	Device name - <i>required</i> Info <input type="text" value="/dev/sdb"/>
Snapshot Info <input type="text" value="Don't include in launch template"/>	Size (GiB) Info <input type="text" value="10"/>
Volume type Info <input type="text" value="gp3"/>	IOPS Info <input type="text" value="2000"/>
Delete on termination Info <input type="text" value="Don't include in launch template"/>	Encrypted Info <input type="text" value="Don't include in launch template"/>
KMS key Info <input type="text" value="Don't include in launch template"/>	Throughput Info <input type="text" value="125"/>

KMS keys are only applicable when encryption is set on this volume.

Figure 61. Adding Security Groups for ABL

Creating of ASG:

After having a template, next is creating an Auto Scaling Group by setting the following information:

- **ASG name** : ASG01
- **Template** : TC01
- **VPC** : Default VPC
- **Availability Zones and subnets** : Select All
- **Load Balancing** : Attach on existing Load Balancer
- **Existing load balancer target groups**: TGN01
- **Health checks** : Check ELB, 120 seconds
- **Desired capacity** : 2
- **Minimum capacity** : 1
- **Maximum capacity** : 5

After completed creating the ASG (Auto Scaling Group) is displayed in the list.

Figure 62. Listing ASG

6.2. Django Web-Based Application Development

6.2.1. Login Page

First web page while accessing to the system is login page. The credential is the same as admin's Django.

Figure 63. Login Page

6.2.2. PTC Workshop Home Page

After logging in, there is a home page of PTC Workshop which display total records of attendance, car (vehicle), invoice, product, salary, staff, stock and utility.

Figure 64. PTC Workshop Home Page

6.2.3. PTC Workshop Attendance Page

In attendance page displays related information such as id, staff, date, status, reason. Especially, it shows the total row of attendance dataset as well. Moreover, id and staff can be searched, sorted and also can be print as a report.

ID	Staff ID	Date	Status	Reason
16	8	2022-05-27	0	busy
17	8	2022-05-27	0	
18	7	2022-06-01	0	Busy
19	8	2022-05-28	0	Busy
20	9	2022-05-28	0	Sick

Figure 65. PTC Workshop Attendance Page

6.2.4. PTC Workshop Car Page

In car page displays related information such as id and brand, especially, it shows the total row of car dataset as well. Moreover, id and brand can be searched, sorted and also can be print as a report.

ID	Brand
96	Camry 02
97	Camry 97
98	Lexus 470
100	Lexus RX 300
101	Lexus RX 330
...	...

Figure 66. PTC Workshop Car Page

6.2.5. PTC Workshop Sale Statistic Page

In sale statistic page displays related information of invoice income in USD such as total, mean, mode, median, range, variance, standard deviation and skewness.

The screenshot shows a web interface with a navigation menu on the left and a main content area. The navigation menu includes links for PTC Home, Attendance, Car, Sale Statistic (highlighted), Sale Regression, Sale Prediction, Product, Salary, Staff, Stock, and Utility. The main content area is titled "PTC Workshop / Sale Statistic" and contains a table with the following data:

Statistic	Value (USD)
Total	678135.0149999999
Mean	47.48844642857142
Median	36.0
Mode	10.0
Range	178.0
Variance	1643.4846871434886
Standard Deviation	40.53991474020991
Skewness	1.111148498490739

Figure 67. PTC Workshop Sale Statistic Page

6.2.6. PTC Workshop Sale Regression Page

In sale regression page displays related information of invoice income in USD such as model, R-squared, mean squared error, intercept, coefficients and the best model.

The screenshot shows a web interface with a navigation menu on the left and a main content area. The navigation menu includes links for PTC Home, Attendance, Car, Sale Statistic, Sale Regression (highlighted), Sale Prediction, Product, Salary, and Staff. The main content area is titled "PTC Workshop / Sale Regression" and contains a table with the following data:

Model	R-squared	Mean Squared Error	Intercept	Coefficients
LinearRegression	-0.42	96988534.23	5128129.32	[-25.22]
Ridge	-0.42	96988308.85	5128084.51	[-25.22]
Lasso	-0.42	96988514.57	5128125.41	[-25.22]

Below the table, it states "Best Model: LinearRegression" and "Cross-validated R-squared: -0.47 ± 0.41".

Figure 68. PTC Workshop Sale Regression Page

6.2.7. PTC Workshop Sale Prediction Page

In sale prediction page displays related information of invoice income in USD monthly. Especially, it also display predict data along with the chart.

Figure 69. PTC Workshop Sale Prediction Page – Part 1

Under the chart, there is two tables display about ‘Original Sales Data’ from the dataset and ‘Extended Sales Data (Predicted for the next months)’ from the model.

202407	26154.32
202408	25017.75
202409	26398.8
202410	29447.11
202411	9883.75
Extended Sales Data (Predicted for the next months)	
Sale Date	Predicted Grand Total
202208	24692.52371188358
202209	24688.590284900507
202210	24684.65685791755

Figure 70. PTC Workshop Sale Prediction Page – Part 2

The prediction is dynamic by clicking on the ‘Predict Sales for Next Months’ button, number of months can be input to the model for prediction.

Figure 71. PTC Workshop Sale Prediction Page – Part 3

6.2.8. PTC Workshop Product Page

In product page displays related information such as id, product information, especially, it shows the total row of product dataset as well. Moreover, id and product can be searched, sorted and also can be print as a report.

Figure 72. PTC Workshop Product Page

6.2.9. PTC Workshop Salary Page

In salary page displays related information such as id, staff, date, amount, and bonus. Especially, it shows the total row of salary dataset as well. Moreover, id and staff can be searched, sorted and also can be print as a report.

The screenshot shows a web application interface for 'PTC Workshop / Salary'. On the left is a navigation menu with items like PTC Home, Attendance, Car, Sale Statistic, Sale Regression, Sale Prediction, Product, Salary, Staff, Stock, and Utility. The main content area displays 'Salary - Total Records: 538' and a 'Print Table' button. Below this are search filters for 'Enter ID to search' and 'Enter Staff to search'. A table lists salary records with the following data:

ID	Staff ID	Date	Amount	Bonus
16	8	2022-06-04 00:00:00	300	0
18	9	2022-06-05 00:00:00	290	0
19	7	2022-07-24 00:00:00	300	25
20	11	2022-09-16 00:00:00	280	50
21	12	2022-09-16 00:00:00	220	50
22	15	2022-09-16 00:00:00	220	50

Figure 73. PTC Workshop Salary Page

6.2.10. PTC Workshop Staff Page

In staff frequency table page displays related information ‘tabe_staff_fe.csv’ dataset. It has been transformed from general data to frequency encoding dataset. It shows Age and Experience data. Especially, it shows the total row of dataset and Age and Experience can be searched, sorted and also can be print as a report.

The screenshot shows a web application interface for 'PTC Workshop / Staff Frequency Table'. On the left is a navigation menu with items like PTC Home, Attendance, Car, Sale Statistic, Sale Regression, Sale Prediction, Product, Salary, Staff, Stock, and Utility. The main content area displays 'Staff Frequency Table - Total Records: 22' and a 'Print Table' button. Below this are search filters for 'Filter by Age' and 'Filter by Experience'. A table lists staff frequency data with the following data:

Age	Experience
25	4
31	5
27	5
24	5
25	5
25	4
--	-

Figure 74. PTC Workshop Staff Page – Part 1

Under the table, there is a scatter plot which displaying based on data in the table above.

Figure 75. PTC Workshop Staff Page – Part 2

6.2.11. PTC Workshop Stock Page

In salary page displays related information such as id, staff, date, amount, and bonus. Especially, it shows the total row of salary dataset as well. Moreover, id and staff can be searched, sorted and also can be print as a report.

ID	Product ID	Price	Quantity	Date
2	2750	5	5	2022-11-02 01:57:12
3	2751	0.5	10	2022-11-02 01:59:24
4	2752	25	3	2022-11-02 02:10:52
5	2753	6	5	2022-11-02 02:11:18
6	2754	7	1	2022-11-02 02:23:17
7	2755	8	40	2022-11-02 02:25:11
8	2756	8.5	50	2022-11-02 02:40:50

Figure 76. PTC Workshop Stock Page

6.2.12. PTC Workshop Utility Page

In sale statistic page displays related information of invoice income in USD such as total, mean, mode, median, range, variance, standard deviation and skewness.

DATANA RACHNA COMPUTER PTC WORKSHOP Logout																			
RACHNA Home	<h2>RACHNA Computer / Sale Statistic</h2>																		
Sale Statistic	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Statistic</th> <th>Value (USD)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td>185697.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mean</td> <td>441.0855106888361</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Median</td> <td>465.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mode</td> <td>500.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Range</td> <td>1020.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Variance</td> <td>77229.73615585557</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Standard Deviation</td> <td>277.9023860204435</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Skewness</td> <td>0.533618003885907</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Statistic	Value (USD)	Total	185697.0	Mean	441.0855106888361	Median	465.0	Mode	500.0	Range	1020.0	Variance	77229.73615585557	Standard Deviation	277.9023860204435	Skewness	0.533618003885907
Statistic	Value (USD)																		
Total	185697.0																		
Mean	441.0855106888361																		
Median	465.0																		
Mode	500.0																		
Range	1020.0																		
Variance	77229.73615585557																		
Standard Deviation	277.9023860204435																		
Skewness	0.533618003885907																		
Sale Regression																			
Sale Prediction																			
Categories																			
Customers																			
Products																			
Sales																			
Stocks																			
Suppliers																			

Figure 79. RACHNA Computer Sale Statistic Page

6.2.15. RACHNA Computer Sale Regression Page

In sale regression page displays related information of sale income in USD such as model, R-squared, mean squared error, intercept, coefficients and the best model.

DATANA RACHNA COMPUTER PTC WORKSHOP Logout																					
RACHNA Home	<h2>RACHNA Computer / Sale Regression</h2>																				
Sale Statistic																					
Sale Regression	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Model</th> <th>R-squared</th> <th>Mean Squared Error</th> <th>Intercept</th> <th>Coefficients</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>LinearRegression</td> <td>0.78</td> <td>20050563.37</td> <td>-32156181.8</td> <td>[158.95]</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Ridge</td> <td>0.78</td> <td>20052076.27</td> <td>-32152007.61</td> <td>[158.93]</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Lasso</td> <td>0.78</td> <td>20050571.93</td> <td>-32156158.16</td> <td>[158.95]</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Model	R-squared	Mean Squared Error	Intercept	Coefficients	LinearRegression	0.78	20050563.37	-32156181.8	[158.95]	Ridge	0.78	20052076.27	-32152007.61	[158.93]	Lasso	0.78	20050571.93	-32156158.16	[158.95]
Model	R-squared	Mean Squared Error	Intercept	Coefficients																	
LinearRegression	0.78	20050563.37	-32156181.8	[158.95]																	
Ridge	0.78	20052076.27	-32152007.61	[158.93]																	
Lasso	0.78	20050571.93	-32156158.16	[158.95]																	
Sale Prediction																					
Categories																					
Customers																					
Products																					
Sales																					
Stocks																					

Figure 80. RACHNA Computer Sale Regression Page

6.2.16. RACHNA Computer Sale Prediction Page

In sale regression page displays related information of sale income in USD such as model, R-squared, mean squared error, intercept, coefficients and the best model.

Figure 81. RACHNA Computer Sale Prediction Page – Part 1

Under the chart, there is two tables (figure 75) display about ‘Original Sales Data’ from the dataset and ‘Extended Sales Data (Predicted for the next months)’ from the model.

202406	14738.0
202407	18103.0
202408	22423.0
202409	23463.0
202410	28153.0

Extended Sales Data (Predicted for the next months)

Sale Date	Predicted Grand Total
202311	2077.931790046394
202312	2247.8702874183655
202401	17372.39655404538
202402	17542.3350514248

Figure 82. RACHNA Computer Sale Prediction Page – Part 2

The prediction is dynamic by clicking on the ‘Predict Sales for Next Months’ button, number of months can be input to the model for prediction.

Figure 83. RACHNA Computer Sale Prediction Page – Part 3

6.2.17. RACHNA Computer Category Page

In utility page displays related information category especially, it shows the total row of table as well. Moreover, id and category name can be searched, sorted and also can be print as a report.

Figure 84. RACHNA Computer Category Page

6.2.18. RACHNA Computer Customer Page

In customer page displays related information customer especially, it shows the total row of table as well. Moreover, id and customer name can be searched, sorted and also can be print as a report.

Figure 85. RACHNA Computer Customer Page

6.2.19. RACHNA Computer Product Page

In product page (figure 79) displays related information product especially, it shows the total row of table as well. Moreover, id and description can be searched, sorted and also can be print as a report.

Figure 86. RACHNA Computer Product Page – Part 1

Under the table, there is a vertical bar chart which displaying based on data in the table above.

Figure 87. RACHNA Computer Product Page – Part 2

6.2.20. RACHNA Computer Sale Page

In sale page displays related information sale especially, it shows the total row of table as well. Moreover, id and date can be searched, sorted and also can be print as a report.

The screenshot shows the 'RACHNA Computer / Sales' page. It features a sidebar on the left with navigation links: RACHNA Home, Sale Statistic, Sale Regression, Sale Prediction, Categories, Customers, Products, Sales, Stocks, and Suppliers. The main content area displays a table of sales records with the following data:

ID	Date	Customer	Total USD	Total R	Total B	Dis. USD	Dis. R	Dis. B	Gr. USD	Gr. R	Gr. B	P. USD	P. R	P. B
87	2024-01-11 00:00:00.0	1	465.0	1860000.0	13950.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	465.0	1860000.0	13950.0	465.0	1860000.0	13950.0
88	2024-01-11 00:00:00.0	1	500.0	2000000.0	15000.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	500.0	2000000.0	15000.0	500.0	2000000.0	15000.0
93	2024-01-05 11:58:13.0	1	500.0	2000000.0	15000.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	500.0	2000000.0	15000.0	500.0	2000000.0	15000.0
99	2024-01-08 12:04:05.0	1	180.0	720000.0	5400.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	180.0	720000.0	5400.0	180.0	720000.0	5400.0
101	2024-01-11 12:15:52.0	1	300.0	1200000.0	9000.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	300.0	1200000.0	9000.0	300.0	1200000.0	9000.0
Total Rows: 5									Gr. USD Sum: 1945.00					

Figure 88. RACHNA Computer Sale Page

6.2.21. RACHNA Computer Stock Page

In stock page displays related information stock especially, it shows the total row of table as well. Moreover, id and product can be searched, sorted and also can be print as a report.

Figure 89. RACHNA Computer Stock Page

6.2.22. RACHNA Computer Supplier Page

In supplier page displays related information supplier especially, it shows the total row of table as well. Moreover, id and supplier name can be searched, sorted and also can be print as a report.

Figure 90. RACHNA Computer Supplier Page

7. Project Management

Palasamudram (2023) stated, “Project Management is the process of planning and executing projects. Project managers use their techniques and resources in order for their team to achieve their objectives before the deadline.” Project management principle is very important for application development. The Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) is a process used to design, develop, and test software to ensure high quality. Its goal is to create software that meets customer expectations, stays on schedule, and fits within budget. SDLC provides a detailed plan for developing, maintaining, updating, or improving software, focusing on improving quality and the overall process (*SDLC - Overview*, n.d.).

7.1. Time Management and Task Prioritization

Effective time management was critical to the successful completion of this project, given its complex scope and tight deadlines. There are 5 primary phases were used to ensure the project was completed on time. They are Initial Planning and Data Gathering, System Design and Architecture, Development and Implementation, Testing and Optimization, and Deployment and Final Review.

The Initial Planning and Data Gathering: This phase focused on understanding the business requirements of the PTC Workshop and RACHNA Computer. The scope was refined, and the necessary data for both companies was gathered from their existing MySQL databases.

System Design and Architecture: A detailed system architecture was developed to integrate Apache Hadoop, Sqoop, and the Django framework with AWS services. This phase also included the selection of the appropriate EC2 instance types and setting up the environment on Ubuntu Linux.

Development and Implementation: During this phase, the core functionalities of the system were developed, including the integration of Hadoop and Sqoop for data transfer, building the Django web application, and creating regression models for income prediction.

Testing and Optimization: The system was thoroughly tested to ensure the stability of the infrastructure, the accuracy of the predictions, and the scalability of the web application. Performance tuning was carried out on the Hadoop cluster and the Django application to handle the expected load.

Deployment and Final Review: The project was deployed on AWS EC2, and the performance was monitored using the Application Load Balancer and Auto Scaling Group. The final results were reviewed with stakeholders.

By clearly defining deadlines for each phase and adhering to a schedule, the project was completed on time without significant delays. Time management tools like Gantt charts were used to track progress, ensuring that tasks were completed in sequence and without overlap.

Priority	Tasks	Duration	October 14, 2024	October 21, 2024	October 28, 2024	November 4, 2024	November 11, 2024	November 18, 2024
1	Initial Planning and Data Gathering	7 Days						
2	System Design and Architecture	7 Days						
3	Development and Implementation	14 Days						
4	Testing and Optimization	7 Days						
5	Deployment and Final Review	7 Days						
total	6 Tasks	42 Days						

Figure 91. Project development schedule Gantt Chart

7.2. Risk Management in Project Management

Data Transfer Issues: The transfer of bulk data from MySQL databases to Hadoop using Sqoop posed a risk of data corruption or incomplete transfers. This risk was mitigated by conducting multiple test transfers before performing the final data import. Additionally, data integrity checks were incorporated into the workflow.

System Downtime and Performance: Project’s running is on cloud infrastructure, there was a risk of downtime or slow performance during high demand. To fix this, AWS Auto Scaling Group (ASG) was used to automatically add or remove EC2 instances based on the load. An Application Load Balancer (ALB) was also used to spread traffic evenly across instances.

Accuracy of Predictions: Accurate income prediction was key to the project's success, but there was a risk that the regression models might not perform well. To address this, a thorough validation process was done. The models were trained with historical data and tested for accuracy using cross-validation techniques.

Security and Compliance: Since the project involved sensitive business data, security and compliance risks were addressed by encrypting data both at rest and in transit. Best practices in cloud security were followed, and regular backups were scheduled to protect data integrity.

7.3. Communication and Collaboration with Stakeholders

Communication and collaboration with stakeholders was occurred for the whole project to ensure that the system met the user’s requirements of both PTC Workshop and RACHNA Computer.

Instant Messaging Platform: Telegram application is used to communicate the whole project for messaging, sending, and receiving data and non-real-time discussion. Related stakeholders, including business owners and technical team members, were regularly updated via this communication platform to ensure a transparent flow of information.

Figure 92. Telegram’s group for project communication

Online Meeting Platform: Google Meet is a simple and free-of-charge platform used for real-time discussion the collaborative approach was taken to ensure that the requirements of both

businesses were properly understood and incorporated into the project design. This collaborative effort helped fine-tune the output to provide actionable insights for business decision-making.

Figure 93. Google meet for project communication

Collaboration with Stockholders: The project has been planned and analyzed by discussing with the owner of the company to understand the user requirements. Figures 87 and 88 below are the draft of the current system from the owner of the company that needs to be studied. Then, the new system is discussed to ensure that everything is matched to the user requirements, aligned with the project’s objective, and full functionalities for stack holders to use.

Summary

Income(I)	Salary Expense(S)	Utility Expense(U)	Profit = I - (S+U)	Spar part (SP)	Net Income (NI) = I - SP

Spar part = Total Invoice - labor cost

Service Profit = Service (invoice) - Salary - Utility.

Figure 94. Draft of the current PTC Workshop web-based application

- I - Invoice Management
 - II - Spare Part Management
 - III - Staff Management
 - List staff
 - Salary
 - IV - Income/Expense
 - Net Income
 - All Income
 - All Salary
 - All Asset
- } අයිටිමස් ප්‍රවේශනය
 } අයිටිමස් ප්‍රවේශනය

Figure 95. Draft feature of the current PTC Workshop web-based application

Figure 96. Draft of planning for the web-based application processing

Conclusion

This Capstone Project solved the real-world problem of PTC Workshop and RACHNA Computer companies by developing a web-based application to centralize, analyze, and visualize data for the existing database of the companies. The project provides a primary functionality related to static data especially it can predict invoice income for the future, it means PTC Workshop can visualize data of the prediction of the income of next months from invoices. It also provides many secondary functionalities such as vehicle brand numbers, invoice number or sale statistics data, a summary of the total price of invoices for all days or separated by month and year, and product quantity in inventory. RACHNA Computer can produce statistical reports related to sales, products, categories, staff, or suppliers. The owner of the company to see more about many functionalities related to statistical data including the number of products, categories, and suppliers, number or summary of sales for the whole records or separated by month and year. And RACHNA Computer can predict the income for the next months from sales data. Even though there are a few risk management to concern, including Data Transfer Issues, System Downtime and Performance, Accuracy of Predictions, and Security and Compliance, many languages, frameworks, tools, and services such as Apache Hadoop, Apache Sqoop, Python, Django, Amazon Web Services, EC2, Ubuntu Linux, EBS, ABL, ASG are combined to develop and operate this project completely and successfully.

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ITDS680 - Assignment Rubric
Capstone Project Route

Student's Full Name: MONY HO

EIU ID: EIU95527

Category	Marks Allocation	Marks Attained	Comments
1. Problem Statement and Project Scope	10 marks	7	
2. Literature Review	10 marks	7	
3. Data Collection and Preprocessing	10 marks	8	
4. Data Analysis and Modelling	30 marks	26	
5. Results and Discussion	20 marks	20	
6. Implementation and Deployment	10 marks	7	
7. Project Management	10 marks	7	
*** Penalty *** This penalty is for papers that do not meet the assignment requirements. (i.e. word count, format, etc.)	(-5)		
Total marks allocated and achieved:	100 marks	82	